

D5.1 Pilot Requirements & Usability Evaluation

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Abstract	<p>The document outlines the pilot requirements and usability evaluation framework for the ELOQUENCE project. It describes four pilots focused on safety-critical, smart home, and social assistant scenarios, highlighting their goals, technological requirements, and societal challenges.</p> <p>Additionally, the document presents the usability evaluation framework, detailing the metrics, criteria, and KPIs used to assess ELOQUENCE technologies. The evaluation aims to measure user acceptance and the effectiveness of the tools in real-world scenarios, driving continuous improvements in line with the project's objectives and ethical considerations.</p>			

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AHT	Average Handle Time
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ASA	Average Speed of Answer
ASR	Automatic Speech Recognition
BCM	Background Comparison Metric
BLEU	BiLingual Evaluation Understudy
CCR	Call Containment Rate
CES	Custom Effort Score
CLI	Command Line Interface
CSAT	Customer Satisfaction Score
CSI	Customer Satisfaction Index
DP	Differential Privacy
FCR	First Call Resolution
FIR	Factual Information Retrieval
FL	Federated Learning
FT	Fine Tuning
GA	Grant Agreement
GSM-8K	Grade School Math 8K
IP	Interactive Playground
KB	Knowledge Base
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
KR	Key Result
KSVear	Knowledge, Skills, and Values Evaluation for Artificial Agents and Robotics
KWS	Keyword Spotting
LLM	Large Language Model
MMLU	Massive Multitask Language Understanding
NPS	Net Promoter Scale
PCM	Pairwise Comparison Metric

RAG	Retrieval Augmented Generation
REST	Representational State Transfer
ROUGE	Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation
SF	Satisfaction Feedback
TTS	Text to Speech
UMUX	Usability Metric for User Experience Questionnaire
UX	User Experience
VA	Virtual assistants

Executive Summary

The document delineates various use cases, requirements and anticipated results for each pilot project. It defines the KPIs, the evaluation criteria and the methodology we propose to assess the feasibility, usability, and potential impact of ELOQUENCE in these envisioned scenarios. The provided definitions are in line with the project's goal to achieve **Objective 4** (Definition of a framework to assess the conversational AI methods) and **Objective 5** (Definition and execution of pilots to validate ELOQUENCE technologies).

Overall, the following Sections address:

- A detailed description of the pilots, highlighting their goals and the specific issues to be addressed.
- A more technical presentation of the pilots, discussing the main challenges, innovations, requirements, and results for each scenario.
- The usability evaluation framework, characterized by criteria, metrics, and KPIs for the different pilots, along with the design applied to conduct the evaluation.

One of the paramount cross-pilot requirements involves the Interactive Playground (IP), a platform for gathering and exhibiting the adapted LLMs and conversational technologies. The IP relates to task 5.3, started in month 10 and concluding at month 18, that will act as the primary infrastructure supporting the pilot's execution and will offer continuous feedback to WP1-4. Throughout the various pilot descriptions and summaries, in Section 2, we detail the essential technologies that need to be integrated and tailored within the IP.

The baseline and metrics detailed in Section 3 focus on the call centres scenario and are related to **KR11 to KR15**, which assess the needed improvements for both enhancing efficiency, by reducing operational cost, and for increasing the customer satisfaction, by efficiently handling calls. The **KR11** is related to increasing the First Call Resolution (FCR) in call centres and **KR12** aims to double the satisfaction feedback for call centre deployments, with methodologies and tools specified in Section 3.5. **KR13** targets a 50% increase in the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI), with relevant methodologies and tools described in Section 3.5 and Appendix 6.4 and 6.5. For the **KR14**, which seeks to improve call containment by 20%, we develop baseline metrics within the Sections 3.3 and 3.4, aiming to reduce the need for call transfers to human representatives. Finally, for the **KR15** that addresses safety-critical applications, metrics are defined across the Section 3, ensuring comprehensive safety measures.

Advancing towards the achievement of **KR16 to KR18**, we focus on the necessary technologies and metrics for demonstrating virtual agents in various scenarios, not only including call centre safety-critical situations but also in smart home environments and social situations. These demonstrations will be essential for validating the effectiveness and bias mitigation of virtual agents in real-world applications.

The effort in this deliverable sets the stage for achieving the milestone 5.1, "Pilots Baseline and Interactive Playground," ensuring all necessary elements are prepared for the subsequent implementation of the different pilots. The results of the performed evaluation will be provided in the cross-pilot deliverable 5.4

1 Introduction

ELOQUENCE focuses on researching and developing innovative technologies for collaborative voice and chatbots capable of managing unstructured dialogues. The aim is to validate these technologies through safety-critical applications, smart home environments, and social scenario assistants, ultimately striving for safer voice assistant systems.

The technologies developed by ELOQUENCE will be tested through four main pilot projects that address safety-critical applications, smart home scenarios, and social assistant roles.

The document outlining these pilots and the evaluation framework designed considering the Key Results (KRs) in the Grant Agreement (GA) and related to the Objectives 4 and 5:

- Objective 4: Definition of a framework to assess conversational AI methods across various scenarios (KR-11, KR-12, KR-13, KR-14, KR-15).
- Objective 5: Definition and execution of pilots to validate ELOQUENCE technologies (KR-16, KR-17, KR-18).

How the various KRs will be achieved during the project is presented in the manuscript and summarized in the following Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of considered KRs

OBJ ID	KR ID	Description	Validation
4	KR11	Increasing First Call Resolution by 20% relative for call centre deployment	Baseline and metrics to consider are reported in Section 3.3.
	KR12	Increase satisfaction feedback by 100% for call centre deployment	Methodology and tools are reported in Section 3.5.
	KR13	Increase Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) by 50%	Methodology and tools are reported in Section 3.5 and Appendix 6.4.
	KR14	Increase call containment by 20% relative	Baseline and metrics to consider are reported in Sections 3.3 and 3.4.
	KR15	Relevant metric for safety-critical applications	Defined metrics for the different scenarios are reported in Section 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4.
5	KR16	Demonstrate virtual agent for call centre safety-critical scenario	The results of the evaluation of the pilot 3 and 4 will be reported in D5.4.
	KR17	Demonstrate virtual agent for smart home scenario	The result of the evaluation of the pilot 1 will be reported in D5.4.
	KR18	Demonstrate virtual agent in social situations and evaluate possible biases exhibition	The result of the evaluation of the pilot 2 will be reported in D5.4.

2 Pilot presentation, requirement analysis, use case assets and participatory design

This Section outlines the four pilots proposed in the project, detailing how they are applied to the various scenarios considered while emphasizing the objectives and specific needs they aim to address.

The four pilots presented in Figure 1 and led by TID, CNR, OM and UNS, respectively, will be our test-bed environment for testing and validating the new ELOQUENCE technologies. The pilots are equally distributed between smart home and social scenarios, pilots 1 and 2, and safety-critical contact centre scenarios, corresponding to pilots 3 and 4.

Figure 1 Pilots ID, title and considered scenario

The different pilots will exploit the technologies developed by all the WPs, providing valuable insights to drive possible redesigns. As shown in Figure 2, the piloting validations are tightly connected with all R&D WPs and deal with the integration of project components, the production of datasets and the collection of feedback for their improvement. To facilitate the integration carried out in the pilots, an IP will be developed to embed and display the LM and ELOQUENCE tools used across the various pilots. The tools embedded in the IP will be contextualised in the specific use cases and customised according to each pilot data and dialogue flow.

Figure 2 Relation of Pilots with project WPs

In the following sections, the pilot descriptions and technological requirements are outlined, alongside an exploration of the societal challenges and key pilot assets within the ELOQUENCE framework.

Starting from the identification of the specific needs of each pilot, initial mappings with ELOQUENCE tools and their configurations are provided. To ensure a broader impact, special attention is given to framework generalisation capabilities and cross-requirements to different end users, business cases and application domains.

Finally, the Section also outlines the approach for engaging stakeholders and business units, aiming to involve them in validating requirements and anticipated outcomes. This will be mainly achieved through workshops/virtual meetings with business stakeholders, developers of third-party applications, and other relevant members within the ecosystem.

2.1 Pilot 1: “Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralised training in smart homes”

2.1.1 Pilot description

Privacy-preserving and domain adaptation of AI models is a cornerstone in any end-user AI application. The main objective of the current pilot is showcasing a framework enabling AI models to be globally trained but, at the same time, locally adapted to user’s data while ensuring privacy.

By using a privacy-preserving framework, multiple parties can be capable of taking profit of a generic model globally updated in cloud/edge facilities, while adapt and personalize, e.g., their LLMs and ASR model. In the case of LLM and speech models training, the produced models should ensure personalization, adaptability and security, that is, avoiding the risk of personal data leakages while improving or incorporating new functionalities to the original models, e.g., multilingual capabilities.

For this purpose, we propose developing a pilot relying on the Federated Learning (FL) paradigm and with applications within the domestic environment. The FL framework is designed to demonstrate both efficacy and efficiency of privacy-preserving training and evaluation techniques for AI systems on the edge or cloud. The computing/training nodes can be part of heterogeneous computing environments, such as end-user’s devices, edge nodes in a telecommunications infrastructure or high-performance computing platforms in the cloud.

In this FL framework, our approach consists of sharing the end-user's AI models rather than directly their raw personal data, thereby maintaining the secrecy of the client's personal data. The main pilot goal is to showcase the practicality of the iterative adaptation of local LLMs/ASR models by integrating local and external models, e.g., by simulating merging models from one household with those from multiple households or even with models from completed unrelated domains. Data from each household shall remain private, thereby improving the security and privacy of each individual client contributing to the global/shared model and avoiding for a centralized data storage.

The proposed FL architecture will enable individual clients both (1) to locally personalize an artificial intelligence model on its own private data and (2) to perform further adaptation and bolster local models through external data in a high-performance infrastructure, usually in the cloud. For doing so, we propose that each client locally refines its model and then shares its local model’s parameters to a central training server, thus avoiding directly transmit user’s private data to a central server in the cloud, see Figure 3. Note that only some model parameters — local weights — are shared with a central server. In the central server, a global model is concurrently trained and refined by incorporating insights from the entirety of all client models and finally shared back again to each end-user. As seen in Figure 4, an aggregation mechanism is placed on the cloud provider to combine the local model, e.g. local weights — w and w^* in Figure 4, — into an aggregated global model.

Figure 3 Federated Learning paradigm example in domestic environments

The FL methodology augments the local models by leveraging insights from all devices while guaranteeing that raw personal data remains unexposed, thus improving privacy in comparison with classical centralized training. Furthermore, by applying the FL framework, e.g. to LLMs and speech models, we open the door to personalized AI models that can adapt to individual user preferences while proficiency in other domains. The global model retains or even improves the functionality of the individual models, achieving personalization without risking data leakage.

Although at the core of this pilot resides the concept of federated fine-tuning; to further strengthen privacy compliance, we will additionally require privacy mechanisms to apply on shared models, thereby bolstering data privacy and strengthening protection against potential malicious attacks.

Alongside the federated framework itself, and aiming to assess the performance of FL adapted models and a virtual assistant within a simulated domestic environment, other required technologies will be integrated into this pilot:

- ASR module to transcribe audio inputs.
- Key-word spotting (KWS) module to detect “OK, Aura” phrase to trigger a direct conversation with the IP.
- Diarization module to identify and distinguish speakers’ voices in conversational audio inputs.
- LLM module for context-aware, information retrieval and text summarization tasks.

Although our primary goals are (1) to equip the consortium with the essential tools for the efficient federation of models and (2) to conduct evaluations within a domestic setting, we also aim to expand the scope of the model capabilities by incorporating the pilots 2 and 4 into the federation process, thereby enriching the global model with broader and more diverse domains. Therefore, the proposed federation framework will operate on two different hierarchical levels:

- The *Low Federation* level: Which involves distributed learning across simulated households, with multiple devices/clients within each household participating.
- The *High Federation* level: Which integrates models from other partner institutions into the federation process.

Figure 4 Overview of FL models and client's component

These two hierarchical levels are designed to demonstrate the cross-domain capabilities that the aggregated model can achieve via a federation fashion. Note that this approach enables multiple parties—including internal Telefónica units and external third parties—to develop high-performing and personalized LLMs, adapted to several domains while keeping private the user's interactions but, at the same time, getting benefit from each party.

The resulting tools from this pilot will be of interest not only for ELOQUENCE's partners, but for a variety of Telefónica products and services such as the cognitive personal assistant (AURA) and the Movistar TV recommendation apps.

2.1.2 Societal challenges

The rapid advancements in AI are revolutionizing smart home assistants, making them more capable and user-friendly than ever before. These intelligent systems can manage a variety of tasks, from controlling home appliances to providing personalized recommendations, thus significantly enhancing the convenience and efficiency of our daily lives. However, as these technologies become more integrated and invasive within our homes, the importance of data privacy cannot be overlooked. Ensuring that user's data remains secure and private is paramount.

In the light of this, the development of our framework is driven by the motivation to enhance the user experience of smart homes through the creation of personalized and context-aware AI agents, all while maintaining stringent user privacy standards. This initiative addresses several key societal challenges, including the need to ensure that user data remains private and secure, fostering trust in personalized smart home agents, and developing agents capable of learning and adapting to user's context and preferences without compromising privacy.

To achieve this personalization, the proposed framework will allow AI models learning, e.g. from user preferences, specific language, or life routines. Crucially, this training will be implemented in a privacy-preserving manner using the federated learning paradigm, that ensures personal data remains within the residential space while only models or parts of them are shared.

The resulting framework will significantly enhance the agility of the development cycle across product developments in Telefónica for smart domestic environments. This will enable the faster incorporation of advanced language models into Telefónica's end-user applications, ultimately leading to more responsive, secure, and user-friendly smart home environments.

To earn stakeholder endorsement, we will highlight the importance of maintaining high privacy standards when using these personalized home assistants and point out how more potential users could benefit from adopting them once these privacy aspects are satisfied.

2.1.3 Existing and future assets and resources

For assessing the development, efficiency and generalization capabilities of the proposed FL framework, we need to employ several public training and evaluation datasets focusing on training methodologies and architectures related to LLMs, like those proposed in the T2.1 and T2.2 from WP2. Note that similar results are expected to be obtained for ASR models and corresponding datasets, that employ similar transformer-based architectures. For the validation of the distributed FL framework, that involves experiments with a cloud server and several clients in a network we will require the using of several datasets. Additionally, these datasets will shed light on the comparison of the proposed FL framework against a traditional stand-alone training, where we just fine-tune a single model in a centralized manner.

Datasets

- Alpaca** (Taori, et al., 2023): A popular instruction-tuning dataset consisting of more than 52K instructions in English. It includes natural language questions and responses for various NLP tasks such as text generation, translation, open QA, etc., and a wide range of domains, such as math, text processing or code generation. Originally the dataset aims to train/evaluate the model’s ability in following instructions and producing accurate responses, thus assessing its natural language understanding, reasoning, and task completion across various domains. For tailoring the dataset to the pilot’s requirements, it will be split into different partitions, without overlapping, with the aim of simulating independent end-user’s personal data, thus mimicking interactions occurring in a household.

```

{
  "instruction": "Give three tips for staying healthy.",
  "input": "",
  "output": "1.Eat a balanced diet and make sure to include plenty of fruits and vegetables. \n2. Exercise regularly to keep your body active and strong. \n3. Get enough sleep and maintain a consistent sleep schedule."
},
{
  "instruction": "What are the three primary colors?",
  "input": "",
  "output": "The three primary colors are red, blue, and yellow."
},
{
  "instruction": "Evaluate this sentence for spelling and grammar mistakes",
  "input": "He finnished his meal and left the resturant",
  "output": "He finished his meal and left the restaurant."
},
}

```

Figure 5 Example of Alpaca Instruction tuning dataset

- ELOQUENCE** (2025): A new dataset is needed for comparing the decentralized FL-trained of LLM/ASR models against a classical FT in real domestic environment. For doing so, we propose to record real interactions in Spanish within a recreated domestic environment: The User Experience Lab (UX Lab) from TID. The aim is to simulate common everyday conversations among household members. The resulting dataset will consist of audio recordings and their human-validated transcriptions, along with annotated speaker turns, manually curated and annotated. Each dialogue will comprise several turns and will follow a similar formatting as the Fused Dataset produced by the T1.1-1.2 from the WP1, that is used for adaptation of ELOQUENCE’s technologies to conversational data. The ELOQUENCE dataset will allow the pilot to evaluate both classical FT models and the proposed FL models in tasks like as slot-filling, summarization and multilingual generalization within a real domestic environment for both text and speech modalities.

ELOQUENCE dataset script and transcription example:

Scene: Living room (Another conversation about soccer)

The actors (TID employees) are instructed before being recorded with a its role and context situation summary.

Characters:

- **Mum** (Linda González)
- **Dad** (Javier González)
- **Tommy** (10 years old)
- **Alex** (Tommy's friend, also 10 years old)

Context situation: "Linda and Javier, the parents, are at home with their child, Tommy and a friend of Tommy, Alex. The father has just brought them home from a soccer practice. The parents talk to the children about their experience in training and their preferences for players. It's not necessary to be direct in knowing the answers or repeating the exact phrases we have given as examples. We want you to improvise and have a natural conversation while playing Trivia or doing activities around the house. For example, "do you want me to prepare you something to eat?" Or anything else that might come up in a conversation between parents and children. Anything you come up with to continue the conversation and make it flow naturally is fine."

Figure 6 Digital UX lab (top) and dialog excerpt (bottom)

Dialog:

Turn 12:

Mum: So, boys, how was soccer practice today?

Tommy: It was great, Mum! We played a match, and my team won!

Turn 13:

Dad: Nice! Who was the star player?

Alex: **Tommy scored two** amazing goals!

Turn 14:

Mum: Wow, Tommy! Looks like you're becoming a real pro.

Tommy: I'm trying, Mum. Mbappé is my inspiration.

By using the recorded conversations in the ELOQUENCE dataset, the Pilot 1 will evaluate the understanding capabilities of the ELOQUENCE's agents, e.g. on extracting specific information in unstructured dialogues, like as "Tommy scored two goals" – see the example in Figure 6.

Finally, aiming to assess generalization capabilities of the FL approach, we will make use of two more out-of-domain datasets:

- **MMLU** (Massive Multitask Language Understanding, (Hendrycks, et al., 2020)): A comprehensive benchmark designed to evaluate a model's broad knowledge and reasoning capabilities. It consists of approximately 1,000 multiple-choice questions, covering 57 task categories across a wide range of disciplines, including the humanities, social sciences, and hard sciences. The questions are in English and challenge the model to demonstrate a deep understanding of diverse topics, making it a valuable tool for assessing multitask learning and general reasoning skills across various fields of knowledge.
- **GSM-8K** (Grade School Math 8K, (Cobbe, et al., 2021)): An evaluation dataset designed to evaluate a model's arithmetical reasoning and mathematical problem-solving skills. Consisting of approximately 1,000 math problems in English, this benchmark specifically tests a model's ability to solve complex math tasks, making it an effective evaluation tool for Chain-of-Thought reasoning capability. The problems require logical progression through multiple steps, providing a robust measure of a model's proficiency in handling mathematical challenges.

As a result of this pilot operating effectively, we will obtain a CLI/API tool and the evaluation metrics resulting of the FL trained LLMs and ASR technologies adapted to conversational domain, which can be ideal for smart home applications.

Software

To achieve the integration and deployment objectives, the pilot 1 will need and further develop its own software based on some open-source libraries for FL, such as the **FederatedScope** library developed by Alibaba (Kuang et al., 2023). This software will allow to develop a customized privacy-preserving learning framework and to build up our personalized and privacy-enhanced AI models. FederatedScope is an extensive federated learning platform designed to offer ease of use and adaptable customization for a wide range of federated learning tasks, incorporating numerous features to meet the growing needs of federated and privacy-preserving learning. In our case, we build on top of the LLM branch from the FederatedScope open-source repository¹ and further adapt it to support the FL requirements for LLM/ASR models².

Infrastructure

Infrastructure provided (TID):

- The TID computing hardware and networking infrastructure is used to develop and validate internally the FL privacy-preserving framework and development. To verify the correct operation of the decentralized training, and prior to using machines from other institutions, some tests will be performed using TID's own servers.

External Infrastructure (BSC, CNR and UNS):

- Once the pilot 1 correctly operates and is validated within TID premises, the partners contributing to the pilot will cooperate to integrate the necessary components – see Figure 4, cloud-side – into the CTE-AMD cluster provided by the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre – BSC. It will allow harnessing BSC's computational resources and to establish a truly decentralized training network between different partner institutions at different locations.

The pilot will then leverage the increased number of nodes at BSC to accommodate more clients in the federated learning course – see Figure 4. Additionally, the decentralized FL framework will be accessible to real users through a CLI. At that moment, the rest of partners can incorporate their own clients, e.g. from the other

¹ <https://github.com/alibaba/FederatedScope>

² The current development repository can be accessed from <https://github.com/jordilunque/FederatedScope>, llm-ELOQUENCE and asr branches.

partner institutions, like as CNR and UNS, to join the training course, creating a more realistic distributed learning environment between the HPC cluster at BSC (acting as the cloud provider) and end-users from TID, CNR and UNS clients. This final setup will enable further assessment of the second hierarchy for the proposed FL framework.

2.1.4 Technological requirements and tool mapping

The following tables summarize the necessary technological requirements and tools that will be integrated for the implementation of the Pilot 1. The last column in the Table links the corresponding tool with the current main providers of the technology.

Distributed Federated Learning architecture

The proposed development will provide to the consortium with a main asset: A CLI or simple API for decentralized and privacy preserving FL-training.

Table 2 Technological requirements and tool mapping of Pilot 1

Actual environment	Simulated environment	Tools
The AI-driven agent should iteratively enhance its capabilities through a decentralized training provided by different clients, e.g., households and/or partner pilots, while keeping personal clients' data private.	The AI-driven agent should learn from all the model instances distributed across the clients and enhance the global model through an aggregation mechanism.	Federated learning CLI/API
	Decentralized training and model adaptation should integrate parameter efficient and optimization methods	Parameter Efficient Fine-Tuning and Deepspeed
	To bolster data privacy, in addition to the decentralized training schema, additional privacy mechanism will be adopted in an additional privacy layer.	ϵ -Differential-Privacy

Showcase in a smart home scenario

To assess and validate a **virtual agent**, trained in a privacy-preserving fashion and powered with LLM and ASR capabilities, the Pilot 1 proposes to leverage the ELOQUENCE dataset, see Section 2.1.3, and processing the recorded conversations to perform information retrieval tasks and summarization. For doing so the following requirements and tools have been identified.

Table 3 Technological requirements and tool mapping for testing ELOQUENCE models in simulated domestic environment

Actual environment	Simulated environment	Tools
The system should be able to understand unstructured dialogs in a common domestic situation, and capable to perform information retrieval tasks from user requests in a friendly and conversational manner.	The system should be able to process unstructured dialogues and respond in a friendly, conversational and context-aware manner. For instance, should be able to perform information retrieval and summarization tasks.	Context-aware dialogue systems
		Information retrieval
		Text summarization

The system may recognize speech from users.	The system may process and understand both text and audio interactions as input.	ASR - Spanish
The system may attempt to understand all the users that are participating in the interaction	The system may attempt to diarize the input audio to recognize each of the user's participation in the interaction. For that purpose, off-the-shelf diarization tools will be used.	Speaker Diarization
The system may jump into the conversation whenever the user calls for attention to participate in the interaction.	The system may attempt to detect the trigger word "OK, Aura" for starting a conversation. For that purpose, TID technology (Cámara, et al., 2022) will be used.	Keyword Spotting

2.1.5 Pilot realization

The **main expected outcomes** of Pilot 1 are:

- To develop a **Distributed Federated Learning architecture** operational between the Barcelona Supercomputing Centre - BSC (acting as a cloud provider) and end-users, e.g. the partner institutions. In the proposed architecture, global/federated LLM and ASR models are iteratively updated by partly uploading the local trained models from each client. To achieve successful results, the global model should effectively learn from all distributed clients while ensuring client's data remains confidential.
- To leverage a **Command Line Interface (CLI)** to the ELOQUENCE's consortium allowing the federation of LLM and speech models from different clients/partners and the cloud server (BSC). Allowing flexibility in the client/server configurations and privacy methods.
- To **showcase in a smart home scenario** a personalized, conversational, and context-aware **virtual agent**, powered by LLM and ASR capabilities and trained in a privacy-preserving fashion from several heterogenous clients and datasets.

Table 4 outlines the timeline for the pilot 1's execution. The expected duration for integrating and setting up the technical environment -- Phase II -- falls between M10 and M18. By M16, it is anticipated that the various technology providers and WPs will have delivered the initial prototype versions of the necessary technologies depicted, as shown in Table 3. Phase III involves assessing the integrated technical environment, which includes a fully functioning and distributed FL architecture, along with evaluations of the resulting FL-models as established in Phase I. Feedback and results from the previous evaluations will help to refine the Pilot results during the final Phase IV, which will also demonstrate an FL-trained agent using real users' data.

Table 4 Pilot 1 development timeline

Phase	Time period	Main outcomes
I Baseline	M01-M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of relevant public dataset for in and out domain evaluation of the FL framework • Initial collection of ELOQUENCE evaluation dataset • Establishing initial key performance indicators (KPIs) • Define the corresponding pilot evaluations: operational environment, ELOQUENCE toolset/system configuration, evaluation procedures

II Technical environment	M10-M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Implementation of the technical environment for FL training in a network distributed environment (BSC – TID/CNR/UNS) ● Starting integration of other components relevant for the evaluation of the pilot: ASR/LLM cloud modules and tools, local modules, optimization libraries and privacy-preserving toolset ● Define revised relevant metrics: KPIs-related ● Final collection of ELOQUENCE evaluation dataset
III Evaluation of FL infrastructure	M16-M24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Carry out initial evaluations as defined in Phase I ● Identify elements for revision (e.g., technical toolset/individual components, infrastructure, evaluation procedure) with revision recommendations
IV Technical development and final Evaluation	M19-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Revisions addressing recommendations from Phase III ● Integration of the more advanced technical features from WP2, WP3 and WP4 ● Final evaluation as defined in Phase I and Phase III ● Showcasing of FL-agent in domestic environment

2.1.6 Activities related to stakeholder engagement

To successfully develop the pilot, we will organize a range of stakeholder engagement activities aimed at collecting insights, creating questionnaires, and performing final evaluations. These efforts will include structured consultation sessions, workshops, and user feedback meetings. Moreover, the interactive playground will provide users with hands-on experience to test the pilot and facilitate direct communication between users and developers. This iterative exchange of ideas and feedback will guide us in refining our approach and adjusting the pilot as needed.

Since our pilot centres on federated learning with data privacy as a core focus, we have formulated questions to explore the ELOQUENCE workshop audience's comfort with privacy-preserving measures, their perceptions of any potential system weaknesses, and any key considerations they may have during the pilot testing.

Questions for the audience

Since our pilot addresses federated learning with data privacy as a core focus, we have formulated questions to explore the audience's comfort with privacy-preserving measures, their perceptions of any potential system weaknesses, and any key considerations they may have during the pilot testing.

- Does the explanation of federated learning make you feel more comfortable with the process of training an aggregated model while preserving individual data privacy? Why or why not?
- Do you feel our approach to data security is sufficient to protect sensitive information? What specific security concerns, if any, do you have regarding federated learning as applied in this pilot?
- Are there any weaknesses in our system that you would like us to address?
- As end-users and stakeholders, what is most important to you when testing our pilot?

A preliminary analysis of the results from the workshop held in November 2024 in Novi Sad indicates a strong preference for privacy and data security in implementing federated learning. Stakeholders feel reassured knowing personal data remains on local devices, with only model updates being shared, though they expressed a desire for clearer demonstrations of how privacy is maintained. Security remains a primary concern, particularly concerning safeguarding against hacking, device compromise, and potential data leaks from model parameters. Ensuring robust protections while maintaining transparency about how privacy is enforced is viewed as crucial to building trust. Operational reliability is another focal point, with concerns raised about potential performance impacts, such as system slowdowns or disruptions in low-connectivity environments. Stakeholders also highlighted the importance of seamless integration, ensuring that regular device functions remain unaffected. Transparent communication about privacy measures and the ability to address errors or synchronization issues without

compromising security were noted as essential factors in fostering confidence in the system's efficacy and reliability. More details will be provided in the next Deliverable of WP5.

2.1.7 Generalization capabilities

Although TID's primary focus resides on the conversational household domain for home assistants, our agent is versatile and can be adapted to other use cases requiring dialogue capabilities. In fact, by involving partner institutions in the FL training process, our models benefit from enhanced generalization and gains valuable cross-domain knowledge. However, if the agent still falls short for a specific application, our decentralized FL training framework can help. Our FL toolkit would allow LLMs and speech models to continuously improve with new data in a distributed manner, with privacy as its cornerstone.

Beyond ensuring the functionality of the entire FL framework and integration, further investigation into the capabilities, limitations and the optimization parameters of the developed FL architecture may be pursued. For that purpose, the outcomes from WP2 and WP4 will be incorporated into the FL integration process. It could involve exploring factors such as the optimum number of communication rounds, local data pruning techniques and iterations, type of clients for asynchronous aggregation or the aggregation methods themselves employed to update the global models.

2.2 Pilot 2: “Social context-aware language model detecting biases”

2.2.1 Pilot description

The pilot 2 aims to evaluate the use of ELOQUENCE technologies in social scenarios, focusing on the agent's ability to handle dialogues in a socially appropriate and bias-free manner. It intends to simulate a virtual advisory agent that offers guidance based on user profiles, such as career advice and recommendations in selecting university programs. In this context, factors such as culture, gender, religion and ethnicity may lead to biases in the responses generated by the agent.

One of the main challenges is ensuring that generated conversations reveal biases rooted in social factors. The agent proactively requires the necessary information from the users and provides the best advice based on its understanding of the domain, the user's interests, and the context of the conversation. Pilot 2 address these challenges by (1) equipping the agent with knowledge related to conversational practices, and by (2) exploiting a model based on social practices theory to increase the credibility of generated conversations.

Prompt engineering and bias stimulation strategies are planned to be used to test the agent's responses and reveal conversational steps where social biases may arise.

Pilot 2 requires open datasets and/or synthetic dialogues with synthetic individuals, generated according to personas methodology, to elicit biases that might not appear with real user samples.

Innovations include leveraging textual resources and evaluation strategies to assess LLMs' handling of conversational practices and uncover potential biases in specific social scenarios.

2.2.2 Societal challenges

The growing use of virtual assistants, which are progressively replacing human operators, introduces significant societal challenges. Despite progress beyond traditional chatbot models, these virtual assistants frequently struggle with dynamic, open-domain social conversations, often leading to vague or imprecise responses. This inadequacy may leave users dissatisfied and longing for human interaction. For virtual assistants to be truly effective, they need more than just domain-specific knowledge to offer accurate advice and faithful information. They need to handle conversations in a human-like manner that feels natural, being able to consider the social aspects related to the specific scenario and context in which they are called to operate. This involves understanding user interests also through explicit questioning while ensuring that their responses are free from social biases.

LLMs fine-tuned for specific tasks (such as chatbots, recommendation systems, or content generation), can inherit social biases, e.g. originating from the training data used to develop the foundational model. The initial biases pose

the risk of being amplified in the selected scenario, potentially including biases related to race, gender, age, religion, and other demographic factors.

As these technologies become more widespread, their impact on society grows. Young people, who will interact heavily with LLMs in the next years, can be particularly vulnerable to these prejudices because biased LLMs can reinforce dangerous stereotypes, perpetuating cultural divisions and gender inequality. Thus, addressing these biases and prejudices is essential to ensuring that virtual assistants interact fairly and respectfully. This requires a strategic approach to detecting social biases, which involves stimulating and uncovering these biases during conversations. The idea is to use a combination of automated quantitative metrics and qualitative analysis to identify biases more effectively. The results obtained will constitute feedback for the technical WPs of the project useful for defining mitigation strategies.

To gain stakeholder support, we intent to emphasize the importance of developing fair and reliable virtual assistants that integrate seamlessly into users' lives without reinforcing harmful biases. The benefits to society are significant: reducing biases will lead to more accurate and respectful interactions, thereby enhancing user satisfaction and truthfulness in virtual assistants' interactions. Moreover, by ensuring these systems provide equitable support to all users, regardless of their social group, we contribute to the creation of fairer AI systems.

By addressing these challenges, we expect to improve the ELOQUENCE technology's ability to function effectively in diverse and dynamic scenarios, making virtual assistants more useful and widely accepted.

2.2.3 Existing and future assets and resources

The pilot development involves the realization of datasets and software for the generation of synthetic dialogues and synthetic individuals, generated according to personas methodology. These elements will then be exploited to elicit biases that might not appear in conversations involving real users becoming part of the resources produced by the pilot implementation.

Datasets

Pilot 2 requires the development of the following 3 datasets:

- **Synthetic Personas Dataset:** a set of synthetic profiles generated using the Personas methodology. The dataset aims to capture a wide range of social group combinations, including gender, ethnicity, and religion. A proper prompt engineering is considered to generate profiles, representing diverse social identities. A possible profile composition will be obtained by considering different categories of gender, ethnicity, and religion.
- **Synthetic conversational practices Dataset:** a corpus consisting of unstructured dialogues, in Italian and English. The corpus is instrumental in detecting biases within the conversational language and supporting the eventual definition of mitigation strategies. It should cover conversational advisory scenarios in both professional and academic contexts. It is synthetically generated and annotated according to this possible information: biased groups, user profiles, and identified biases: The biases will be detected and labelled by exploiting well-established measures and/or annotated by users.
- **Domain Knowledge:** dataset composed primarily of unstructured text extracted from websites and documents. It serves as the foundation for generating a large volume of dialogues, ensuring that responses to user queries are based on reliable and well-founded information. The LLM will be grounded in this domain knowledge to guarantee that the LLM provides accurate and relevant responses.

Software

Pilot 2 requires the use of the following software, further developed to reach the pilot goals:

- **Synthetic Personas Generator:** a tool to create fictional characters based on the Personas methodology to represent different user types that might interact with the ELOQUENCE LLM. The tool allows the generation of customizable profiles usable to produce synthetic conversations.
- **Student Simulator:** a tool that allows an LLM to behave like a specific user exploiting the data generated by the Personas Generator. The tool can keep track of specific student's motivations and attitudes.

- **Social Context-Aware Agent:** a tool to create synthetic conversations between two parts: a student and a university advisory. The agent can understand the social context in which it operates, to exploit domain knowledge, and thus to generate dialogues consequently.
- **Conversation Analysis module:** it is a framework of metrics defined in Section 3.2.4 to be used to systematically analyse the LLM output for discovering social biases.

Infrastructure

Figure 7 illustrates the physical deployment of pilot 2. The main components are distributed across the overall infrastructure that includes the CNR Infrastructure and the BSC Cluster. The CNR Infrastructure mainly hosts all dataset storage components (Annotated Dialogue Dataset, Synthetic Conversational Practices Dataset, Domain Knowledge Dataset, and Synthetic Personas Dataset). It also contains two operational components: (1) the Student Simulator and (2) the Conversation Analysis module, which are responsible for interaction simulation and dialogue evaluation, respectively. On the other side, the proposed infrastructure will exploit the high-performance computing environment of the CTE-AMD BSC Cluster for computational-intensive operations. Among these, we can surely mention a set of Large Language Models (LLMs) and two critical components: the Synthetic Personas Generator and the Social Context-Aware Agent. The physical deployment strategy aims for efficient resource distribution and computational task management, with the CNR (the Pilot's leader) overseeing data storage and maintenance, and BSC handling compute-intensive tasks.

Figure 7 Overview of the Infrastructure for Pilot 2

Infrastructure Provided by CNR

- The CNR computing hardware and networking infrastructure will be used to set up the conversational agent relying on a specific orchestrator, generate and annotate the datasets, and test and evaluate the generated dialogues.

External Infrastructure

- Access to the BSC cluster will be exploited to handle potential intensive training processes and large-scale data analysis and to make the developed virtual advisor accessible to users through the interactive playground allowing to perform .

2.2.4 Technological requirements and tool mapping

Table 5 below summarizes the technological requirements and tools necessary for implementing Pilot 2. The last column in each table links the relevant tool to its main technology providers.

Table 5 Technological requirements and tool mapping of Pilot 2

Actual environment	Simulated environment	Tools
<p>The system should be capable of engaging in conversations with students who require advice.</p> <p>The system should collect information from the student also by formulating questions.</p>	<p>The system carry out a text communication with a simulated user who has the characteristics of a student, and manifests predefined social characteristics.</p> <p>The system collects information to learn about the students and their interests. If there is insufficient information, it can ask the user player some questions.</p>	Algorithms to fine-tune an LLM into the conversational target domains (Adapters)
		Information retrieval
		Dialogue Management System
The system offers a summary of the conversation.	The system offer a textual summary of its conversation with the user.	Text summarization
The system is aware of the social context in which it operates.	The system is able to learn the social context in which it operates.	Context-aware dialogue systems
<p>In an evaluation with users, the system should be able to handle communication in a more natural way.</p>	<p>The system can comprehend spoken user input and generate appropriate verbal responses.</p>	ASR - Italian
		Text-to-speech

2.2.5 Pilot realization

The **main expected outcome** of the pilot 2 is:

Provide a methodology for **quantitatively assessing** the utterances generated by the LLM for the presence of social bias, unusual patterns, and emotional contents that are not coherent with the specific socio-cultural context of interaction.

- **Synthetic Dataset of Conversations** in which the identified social biases are labelled.

Table 6 Pilot 2 development timeline

Phase	Time period	Main outcomes
I Baseline	M01-M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset collection Establishing initial key performance indicators (KPIs) Define the corresponding pilot evaluations (synthetic, real users): operational environment, ELOQUENCE toolset/system configuration, evaluation procedures (what measure and how)
II Technical environment	M10-M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of the technical environment (LLM other components relevant for the pilot). Define revised relevant metrics: KPIs-related, project-related (WP1)
III Evaluation on synthetic Data and revisions	M16-M24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out initial evaluation as defined in Phase I on synthetic Data Identify elements for revision (e.g., technical toolset/individual components, infrastructure, evaluation procedure) with revision recommendations
IV Technical development and final Evaluation with users	M19-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revisions addressing recommendations from Phase III Integration of the more advanced technical features from WP2 and WP3 Final evaluation as defined in Phase I and Phase III

Pilot Implementation

Regarding the implementation, the pilot will exploit the IP. The key objectives would benefit from the possibility of grounding the LLM on the scenario Dataset and the collected documents. In the Interactive Playground, we plan to obtain LLM fine-tuning by retrieval-augmented generation techniques. Another desirable option is to design the Conversational Practices on top of the LLM for testing it in the IP, shaping the conversational agent behaviour and driving the flow of interactions to align with the desired objectives. And of course, while playing the scenarios in the IP it will be necessary to collect the data for the assessment phase.

We have outlined an initial framework for the pipeline that will characterize the pilot, with social theories and models guiding the data construction process. These components are crucial for identifying interaction practices, tailoring textual data to specific needs, and establishing interaction rules along with expectations for conversation flow and biases typical of those contexts.

Users will interact with the agent based on the LLM in the IP. These practices will also be instrumental in defining interaction scenarios to be implemented in the IP for data collection and feedback. The evaluation process may include explicit and implicit user feedback, leveraging existing measurement tools or text analysis to identify potentially prejudiced words or expressions and assess coherence with expectations.

Finally, understanding how to retroactively utilize this feedback to enhance the conversational agent based on LLMs will be a critical aspect of the process.

Evaluation steps

Initially, the **quantitative assessment of social bias** will be performed exclusively on a synthetic dataset of conversations, made specifically to test the proposed methodology and elicit specific types of social bias. Subsequently, in a later stage, interaction with users is not excluded to validate the proposed methodology under conditions as close to reality as possible.

First step evaluation/demo using synthetic data:

Operational environment:

- Inputs to the system: Textual interaction.
- System outputs: System responses in a terminal.

System toolset:

- First version of IP, appropriately context-aware LLM (adapted to pilot data)
- Tools for measuring the relevant metrics

Evaluation procedure:

- System Evaluation: involves an analysis of the generated text based on the selected metrics.
- User Evaluation: involves human annotation of the generated conversations based on identified social biases and social appropriateness (how well the conversations align with intended goals and social expectations).

Second step evaluation/demo with users

Operational environment:

- Inputs to the system: Spoken interaction to guarantee a more natural interaction (ASR).
- System outputs: TTS system that offers responses to the user.

System toolset:

- ASR, TTS, consolidated Interactive Playground, appropriately context-aware LLM (pilot data)
- Tools for measuring the relevant metrics

Evaluation procedure:

- System Evaluation: involves an analysis of the users' generated text based on the selected metrics.
- User Evaluation: involves human annotation of the generated conversations based on identified social biases and social appropriateness (how well the conversations align with intended goals and social expectations). Users will also be involved in evaluating their perceived satisfaction with using the system through standard questionnaires defined in Section 3.5.2.

2.2.6 Activities related to stakeholder engagement

To support the pilot effectively, a series of stakeholder engagement activities have been planned, with a particular focus on defining metrics, developing questionnaires, and conducting final evaluations. The involvement of experts is instrumental in gathering input on social dynamics and expectations, which are critical for defining our bias detection metrics and designing relevant questionnaires. We will organize consultation sessions to refine our metrics and evaluation tools. These activities will involve stakeholders in defining the specific criteria for bias detection and developing comprehensive questionnaires. Experts will also be involved in the final evaluation of the generated conversations to gather feedback and ensure that the methodologies and findings are robust.

Our pilot was presented during the ELOQUENCE workshop, which was held in November 2024 in Novi Sad. Several questions were posed to the audience.

Questions for the audience

We propose to ask the audience the following questions:

- What features or capabilities do you believe are essential for the AI assistant described in the introduction?
- What potential benefits do you foresee with the implementation of such a virtual advisor?
- What is the best way to keep you informed about the progress and updates regarding the project pilot?

The preliminary analysis of the feedback gathered during the workshop in Nov Sad underscores the importance of features that ensure the AI assistant operates in a socially sensitive and transparent manner. Stakeholders emphasized the need for bias-free conversations, adaptability to diverse social contexts, and real-time adjustments to enhance the appropriateness of interactions. Transparency through clear explanations of responses was also highlighted as a key factor in building trust and credibility. Additionally, the assistant's potential to support diversity and inclusion and provide equitable advice across varied user backgrounds is seen as a significant benefit, especially in advisory roles for students and job seekers. These insights suggest a strong emphasis on fairness, groundedness, and social adaptability in the assistant's development. More details will be provided in the next Deliverable of WP5.

2.2.7 Generalisation capabilities

The essence of our approach is rooted in the methodology used for constructing and validating datasets. This methodology introduces a robust capability for generalization, enabling the system to extend beyond a single type of conversation or user group. By incorporating knowledge about various domains, user profiles, and practices, the system is designed to generate new, contextually relevant dialogues suitable for a wide range of situations.

The process of evaluating and annotating data is crucial in this regard. By creating and labelling datasets from different domains, the pilot outputs will be useful in a variety of new scenarios. The labelling process will be mainly automatic but supervised by humans. This ensures that the virtual assistant is not limited to specific use cases but it will be exploited to handle a broad spectrum of interactions.

2.3 Pilot 3: *“Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user’s goals, making API calls and respond with empathy”*

2.3.1 Pilot description

In this pilot, we undertake a comprehensive evaluation of the performance and capabilities of the proposed innovative LLM-based virtual agent within the demanding realm of customer service. Our primary objective is to develop and train a highly sophisticated virtual agent utilizing a diverse array of enterprise-specific conversational datasets. These datasets are required to encompass a wide spectrum of industries, ranging from complex financial institutions and insurance companies to essential utility providers. The aim of this training process is to create an adaptable virtual agent that can seamlessly generalize its knowledge and skills to new enterprises without the need for additional fine-tuning using company-specific data.

To facilitate its operations, the virtual agent has access to both structured and semi-structured documents pertaining to each enterprise it serves. This access is crucial as it enables the agent to efficiently retrieve and intelligently utilize relevant pieces of information in response to the varied and often complex requests posed by callers.

In pursuing this goal, we anticipate encountering several challenges that already have been identified. These challenges encompass a range of critical areas:

1. The precise and timely retrieval of factual information from vast databases.
2. The development of sophisticated algorithms to determine when API calls or other specific actions need to be initiated.
3. The ability to respond to user requests with a high degree of accuracy, while carefully avoiding the dissemination of any unverified or undocumented information (viz. hallucinations) that could potentially mislead the caller.
4. The implementation of advanced natural language understanding and dialog-state tracking capabilities, with a particular emphasis on deciphering indirect user responses through pragmatic reasoning.

5. The capacity to accumulate and synthesize user intents and information slots across multiple steps of a dialog, ensuring a coherent and contextually appropriate conversation flow.

Furthermore, the virtual agent is designed with multilingual capabilities, allowing it to communicate effectively in various languages. Additionally, steps are taken to perceive and respond to the user's emotional state throughout the interaction.

To achieve these objectives, we are considering utilising or creating problem-specific specialized training datasets. These datasets require to be carefully selected/engineered to closely mimic the characteristics and nuances of real-world conversations between users and customer service agents of actual enterprises, leveraging the advanced experience of Omilia in the respective fields. Moreover, to enhance the agent's ability to retrieve and utilize relevant information, enterprise-specific documentation is incorporated into the training datasets. This documentation is designed to resemble the actual documentation used by real enterprises, thereby ensuring that the virtual agent's retrieval mechanism is trained on authentic and representative data.

Through this comprehensive approach, we aim to develop a virtual agent that precisely meets the complex demands of modern customer service across a wide range of industries and scenarios.

2.3.2 Societal challenges

Epigrammatically, the key societal challenges associated with the pilot as well as with the pilots of WP5 in general are: (1) Data privacy and security: As the playground allows partners to personalize tools with their own data, ensuring the privacy and security of this potentially sensitive information is crucial. (2) Bias and fairness: When partners tune their models with their (publicly available) data, there's a risk of introducing or amplifying biases. (3) Accessibility of the platform: Making sure the interactive playground is user-friendly and accessible to partners with varying levels of technical expertise. (4) Cross-domain applicability: Addressing the challenge of creating a platform flexible enough to support diverse use cases across different domains.

To motivate stakeholders and enhance the usefulness of our interactive playground, there need to be plans to: (1) Customization Demo: Showcase how partners can easily input their own data and context snippets, demonstrating immediate relevance to their specific use cases. (2) Rapid Testing Interface: Highlight the playground's ability to quickly test multiple LLMs with various prompts, enabling efficient model comparison and selection. (3) Use Case Templates: Provide pre-set templates for common industry applications, allowing quick starts for partners in different sectors.

2.3.3 Existing and future assets and resources

Datasets

All related and necessary datasets will be either provided or constructed by the project partners of the respective work packages.

Software

All involved partners have hands on experience on a comprehensive gamut of frameworks, libraries, and software packages; open-source or commercial. Nevertheless, to preserve open-sources of the developed code, and also, to widen the application range of the pilot's functionality every necessary step will be taken so as to render all outputs far-reaching and open-source. The foundations of this approach will be laid by using open-source LLMs like OLMO, Occiglot, or Salamandra. The main reason of this decision has to do with their open nature that allows for broader experimentation, adaptation, and scrutiny of large language models.

Infrastructure

Omilia as a leading small business enterprise has access to a highly sophisticated cloud infrastructure, hosted on Amazon-AWS, that can efficiently train and evaluate voice-enabled dialog systems at scale. The infrastructure supports using any computational node, whether CPU or GPU, available on the Amazon-AWS platform. In parallel, PoCs of the IP will be implemented by making use of the computational capabilities of BSC. BSC operates (amongst others) a MareNostrum4 CTE-AMD Cluster. Additionally, BSC provides PyCOMPSs/COMPSs programming

frameworks, which streamline application development for distributed computing environments like clouds and clusters.

2.3.4 Technological requirements and tool mapping

From a macroscopic but at the same time descriptive viewpoint the interactive playground will involve a user interface sending requests through an orchestration layer, which manages database interactions, pre-processing of inputs, interaction with a language model, and post-processing of outputs, all running within a containerized environment. Such an approach will allow for a flexible, scalable LLM-powered application that can handle various types of queries and related tasks while maintaining efficiency and modularity. As can be seen in the respective Figure 8 the usual flow of a typical interaction would be: (a) the user submits a query or request through the user interface; (b) the request is sent to the Orchestration Layer via a REST API; (c) the pre-processing component sanitizes and formats the input, potentially enriching it with context from the DB via the DB Client; (d) the updated-enhanced prompt is sent to the LLM through a proxy; (e) the LLM generates a response, which through the proxy is sent back to the orchestration layer; (f) during post-processing the response is extracted and parsed, potentially invoking pre-designated functions if required; (g) the final result is sent back to the interface for display to the user.

Figure 8 Overview of the Architecture for pilot 3

The specific technologies and tools necessary for realizing the interactive playground will include:

1. The LLM (or LLMs) viz. the AI engine at the heart of the system. This is going to be the outcome of the combine efforts of WP 1-4 (and related deliverables) of the project. At a bare minimum, it will generate human-like text, answer questions, and perform various language-related tasks.

2. The orchestration layer which will be the central part of the system with regards to interconnecting and coordinating all the different components and processes. The database will be utilized for storing and quickly retrieving relevant information or embeddings (i.e. vector representations of text) to enhance the LLM's responses as is the case for Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG), which improves the efficacy of LLM applications by leveraging custom data. The DB client will interface with each respective vector database (like Chroma or Qdrant). For querying/retrieval either full-text (OpenSearch) or vector similarity (Pinecone, FAISS) searches will be utilized.
 - a. Pre-processing will perform all the necessary tasks before the inputs reaches the LLM. These might include the following. Sanitization: Remove potentially harmful or unwanted elements from the input. Validation: Ensure the input meets specific criteria or format requirements. Formatting: Structure the input in a way the LLM can best understand and respond to. Adaptation: Take into consideration the type of the task at hand (e.g., question-answering, summarization). Context Prebending: Add relevant background information to the beginning of the prompt. History Incorporation: Include previous interactions to maintain context in a conversation. Semantic Retrieval: Use the vector databases to find and include relevant information in the prompt.
 - b. Post-processing will handle the LLM's output. Its main functions will circle around: Response Extraction: Parse the LLM's response to extract the most relevant parts. Logging: Record interactions, inputs, and outputs for monitoring, debugging, and improvement. Function Invocations: Execute additional operations based on the LLM's output, potentially integrating with other specified services.
3. With the Docker containerization technology each application/scenario alongside with its dependencies will be packaged in a standalone container. This will allow for consistent environments across development and subsequent testing, and for isolation of components for better security and resource management.
4. All the corresponding components will communicate and exchange information with the Representational State Transfer (REST) API. This will ensure modularity, scalability and maintainability of the application. Also, integration of the interactive playground with other services or front ends in the future will be facilitated.

2.3.5 Pilot realization

Essentially the main and primary outcome of this pilot is a fully functional interactive playground platform that collects, combines and merges the project's LLMs and approaches. Based upon ELOQUENCE's findings and innovations, the interactive playground will introduce a unified ecosystem for users to access and utilize.

The duration of the pilot's work packages is set between M10-M28. At a large extent, the efforts and focus of the last months will depend upon the progress of related WPs' outputs and upon the provided feedback. Nevertheless, a first working prototype utilizing at least an LLM (accompanied by basic functionalities and features) has been implemented at M11.

2.3.6 Activities related to stakeholder engagement

The interactive playground will fulfil two important functions. First, it will act as a testing environment for the technologies developed throughout the project. Second, it will serve as a bridge between the project and its various users, including both researchers involved in the project and the ultimate actual end-users. As a result, since the interactive playground is not a standalone feature/technology but instead is tightly connected with the rest of the project WPs and outcomes (mainly WP1-5), the plan is to participate in the majority of stakeholder engagement activities organized by each respective partner including technical presentations, workshops, industry meetups and user feedback sessions. It is important to note that based on the flowing feedback from these activities we aim to remain flexible and responsive to any changes in the engagement strategy as determined by the project consortium. The pilot was presented within the ELOQUENCE workshop, held in November 2024 in Novi Sad. A series of questions were posed to the audience.

Questions for the audience

We propose to ask the audience the following questions:

- Given the plans to operate across a diverse set of modalities (voice and text) and domains, which particular ones do you think should be prioritized?
- Considering the fine-tuning vs the Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approaches that the pilot has the capability to adopt/utilize which one do you think should be finally adopted? Why?
- As end-users and/or stakeholders would you opt for a virtual agent system that is at a large extent pre-defined and pre-trained (and thus gives less -or no room- for adaptation) or the contrary?
- From a User eXperience (UX) perspective which features and characteristics of a virtual agent conversational system would you shortlist as most important?

From a preliminary analysis of the feedback, it is possible to highlight stakeholders' expectations for the virtual agent to provide quick, clear, and empathetic responses while effectively handling complex queries. Accuracy, reliability, and smooth guidance are seen as essential for building trust and ensuring user satisfaction. Privacy and security remain critical concerns, with a strong emphasis on protecting personal information and safeguarding against unauthorized access or data leaks. In terms of bias, stakeholders stress the importance of fairness and equal treatment for all users, while also acknowledging the nuanced need to differentiate between harmful biases and those that may reflect reasonable human behaviour. Consistency and staying on-topic are considered vital for the agent's performance, alongside delivering responses that are both accurate and contextually appropriate. These insights reflect a balanced approach to ensuring technical precision, ethical considerations, and a user-centred experience. More details will be provided in the next Deliverable of WP5.

2.3.7 Generalisation capabilities

Given the interactive playground's (as well as the underlying technologies') features the overall system could potentially be generalized to various applications such as:

Customer Service:

- The system could be deployed across various industries (e.g., telecommunications, retail) to handle customer inquiries.
- It could access company-specific knowledge bases through the DB client to provide accurate, up-to-date information.
- The context-aware capabilities could allow it to understand customer history and preferences, providing personalized support.
- The empathetic response feature could help in handling sensitive issues or frustrated customers more effectively.
- The system could handle multiple languages and operate 24/7, improving customer service availability.

(Non-critical) Healthcare:

- Patient inquiries could be addressed using medical knowledge bases integrated into the DB schema.
- Appointment scheduling could be automated, with the system accessing calendar systems through APIs.
- It could provide personalized health information and reminders based on patient records.
- The empathetic response capability would be particularly valuable in handling sensitive health-related queries.

Public Services:

- Assisting citizens with government processes (e.g., permit applications, tax filing).
- Providing information about public services and facilities.
- Handling non-emergency inquiries to reduce load on emergency services.
- Offering multilingual support for diverse populations.

Finance:

- The system could offer personalized financial advice by analyzing user data and financial market information.
- Market insights could be provided by processing and summarizing financial news and data from various sources.
- The system could assist in fraud detection by identifying unusual patterns in transactions.
- It could guide users through complex financial processes like loan applications or investment decisions.

2.4 Pilot 4: “Upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues”

2.4.1 Pilot description

The goal of the pilot is to provide data necessary for simulation of an environment of unstructured dialogues arising in contact centres offering safety-critical responses, specifically in the healthcare domain. The participants in the dialogue will be human users and an intelligent system intended as support to medical staff offering advice to new parents about issues related to their newborns - prevention, general inquiries, actual situations (including emergency situations). This system should be able to handle the communication with the caller and collect necessary data while waiting for the human agent to become available. The system should have the capability to establish the level of priority of the call as well as to provide a summary of its conversation with the caller in a visually convenient way to the human operator, including structured data obtained from the dialogue, and it should switch to the human agent as soon as one is available.

Multimodal data needed to simulate this environment will contain audio recordings of 150 dialogues acted out according to predefined scripts for the care service provider. Natural speakers will capture the caller's side while both natural speakers and text-to-speech (TTS) will be used on the service provider's side.

2.4.2 Societal challenges

For an intelligent system intended as support to medical staff offering advice to new parents it is crucial to maintain the trust between parents and healthcare providers. For ethical reasons and to avoid any possibility of providing incorrect advice that might have serious consequences, the system will never provide information other than by quoting from a verified database of medical knowledge, and its principal purpose will be to gather information from the caller about the situation with the newborn. The trust will be maintained and reinforced by clearly communicating the role of the AI system to callers and ensuring transparency in how their data will be used. They will be fully informed that they will be about to engage in a conversation with an AI system whose only purpose is to exploit the waiting time more purposefully, and that the advice will be provided by the human expert as soon as he or she becomes available.

The system will help streamline the initial data collection process in a medical call centre, allowing medical experts to focus on more complex tasks, which is expected to reduce the workload and wait times for patients. The system will be able to provide preliminary assessments or help flagging urgent cases, helping experts prioritize and make more informed decisions quickly. The system will provide consistent and standardized initial information, reducing variability in the initial assessment and enabling expert to make better-informed decisions. The proprietary design of the system will ensure that relevant stakeholders influence the featuring of the system, maximizing its usefulness in practice.

The introduction of medical call centres of this type ensures that all parents, regardless of their socioeconomic status, have remote access to medical assistance, and the pilot aims at increasing the efficiency and thus the popularity of such a service. Furthermore, a natural speech interface ensures that there are no disparities in access to this technology.

2.4.3 Existing and future assets and resources

Datasets

Pilot 4 will develop the following 2 datasets:

- A **multimodal corpus of 150 unstructured dialogues in the Serbian language** (audio and corresponding text transcriptions) acted out according to a predefined script, that will serve as a foundation for the development of a system that will support medical personnel offering safety-critical responses to young parents about their newborns. Each dialogue will be accompanied by its summary (e.g. “1 year old baby, temperature 39 degrees, cough and a sore throat”), as well as the level of priority of the dialogue (e.g. “3 on a scale from 1 to 5”). The summary will simulate the summary that the automatic system will create in the actual use case and present it to the human operator once the operator is available and ready to take over from the automatic system. The level of priority is a numerical value that would be constantly estimated during the call by the automatic system in the actual use case to determine the order of assignment of available human experts to callers in queue.

Example:

Caller	System
<p><i>(somewhat worried)</i> HalloBaby, my 8-month-old has suddenly developed high fever, and I'm really worried. What should I do?</p> <p>39 degrees</p> <p>Yes, I have.</p> <p>Yes, I gave paracetamol, but the temperature persists, should I try something else?</p> <p><i>(interrupting)</i> Could you repeat that, please?</p> <p><i>(interrupting)</i> OK, excuse me, I forgot to say that she coughs!</p>	<p>[INTRODUCTORY MESSAGE AND DISCLAIMER]</p> <p>How high the fever is?</p> <p>Have you tried giving your baby a lukewarm bath?</p> <p>Have you tried applying something for keeping the temperature down?</p> <p>I'm not a doctor so I couldn't tell you but the information from our webpage says the following: <i>Ibuprofen can be given to children who are aged 3 months or older and who weigh more than 5kg (11lb). Always read...</i></p> <p><i>Ibuprofen can be given to children who are aged 3 months or older and who weigh more than 5kg (11lb). Always read the instructions carefully, or check with a pharmacist or...</i></p> <p>When did she developed the cough? Oh, there is a nurse available now, I will connect you to her...</p>

As can be seen from the example, the system will **never offer any information** other than quoting from the reference database of medical knowledge, and it will even avoid offering feedback such as “Don't worry, this is quite common”. To avoid any fear from incorrect advice that could have serious consequences, the system will always drive the dialogue so that it assumes the active role and the caller responds to its queries, thus providing data that will be presented to the human expert once he or she takes over.

- A **database of expert medical knowledge in textual format**, most notably in the format of questions and answers, aimed to serve as the basis for automatic generation of a large quantity of new dialogues in which the answers to user queries will be contextualized, which would be sufficient for training an LMM (having in mind that 150 dialogues is far too small a quantity for that). Thus, created dialogues will not generate

new medical knowledge, they will only use the knowledge from the database of expert medical knowledge to drive the dialogue and define most relevant questions for the user.

Software

In pilot 4 its owners will make use of the following software that they own:

- Text-to-speech (TTS) in Serbian language. It should be noted that pilot owners have access to similar software for several other languages (Suzić, 2022) (Croatian, Montenegrin, English, French, Italian, Spanish...). The system possesses a high-quality front end (language processing), but also supports standard XML tags for directly specifying phonetic transcription or intonational events if necessary. Several interfaces are supported, including C++ library, COM, SAPI, MRCP and IP server.

Infrastructure

In the UNS pilot, we will simulate the environment of unstructured dialogues arising in contact centres offering medical assistance. The UNS will collect a data corpus within a staged recording process, to support the development of AI-based recommendation systems assisting medical staff in providing advice and will validate ELOQUENCE technologies in a laboratory condition. For data collection purposes within this pilot, mobile phones will be used to capture multimodal audio corpus.

To simulate an environment of a call centre, the following set of hardware devices, including networking devices, is available:

- To host and run the simulation of a call centre with accompanied ELOQUENCE tools, a UNS server will be considered.
- To interact with a simulated call centre, i.e. to simulate call centre agents and callers, a set of workstations or laptops will be considered.
- To train AI-based ELOQUENCE tools required for pilot execution, BSC has given access to CTE-AMD cluster infrastructure.
- A set of routers, switches and cables will be used to set up a dedicated network for the experiment.
- In simulating actual calls, a set of VoIP telephones will be considered.

2.4.4 Technological requirements and tool mapping

Table 7 summarizes the technological requirements and tools necessary for implementing Pilot 4.

Table 7 Technological requirements and tool mapping of Pilot 4

Actual environment	Simulated environment	Tools
<p>The system should be able to handle telephone communication with the caller while waiting for the human agent to become available</p> <p>The system will switch to the human operator as soon as one is available</p>	<p>The system will carry out speech communication with a computer user for a predefined time</p>	Information retrieval
		Speech recognition
	<p>The system will announce, in a certain random moment, that a human operator is available</p>	Text-to-speech
		LLM driven dialogue management
<p>The system may attempt to establish the level of priority of the call, which would influence the decision to which incoming call a human expert is assigned</p>	<p>The system may attempt to establish the level of urgency of user query, and influence the decision at which moment the human-machine dialogue will be</p>	<p>Call priority establishment (optional)</p>

	terminated by the announcement that a human expert is available	
The system will collect necessary data and offer a summary of its conversation with the caller in a visually convenient way to the human operator	The system will collect necessary data and offer a textual summary of its conversation with the user	Text summarization

Initial deployment plan of the Pilot 4 tools across the infrastructure is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Overview of the Infrastructure for Pilot 4

2.4.5 Pilot realization

Pilot development timeline

Table 8 Pilot 4 development timeline

Phase	Time period	Main outcomes
I. Baseline	M01-M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset collection Define initial relevant metrics: KPIs-related, project-related (WP1) Set the baseline values Define the corresponding pilot evaluations (initial, final): operational environment, ELOQUENCE toolset/system configuration, evaluation procedures (what will be measured and how)
II. Technical development	M06-M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of the corresponding LLMs and other components relevant for the pilot (Table 7) Synthetic data augmentation (optional) Define revised relevant metrics: KPIs-related, project-related (WP1)
III. Evaluation and revisions	M16-M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out initial evaluation as defined in Phase I Identify elements for revision (e.g., technical toolset/individual components, infrastructure, evaluation procedure) with revision recommendations

IV. Technical development	M19-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revisions addressing recommendations from Phase III • Development of the more advanced technical/other features (e.g., Call priority classification)
V. Final evaluation	M33-M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out final evaluation as defined in Phase I and Phase III • Proposal for future pilot exploitation activities

First evaluation/demo (draft):

Operational environment:

- Inputs to the system: Spoken queries/responses to the system outputs, level of difficulty: simple (metric: TBD, WP1)
- System outputs: system responses (in a terminal or possibly graphical user interface through Interactive Playground)
- Infrastructure: as in Section 2.4.3 (possibly stripped down to only the necessary infrastructure to support the relevant toolset)

System toolset:

- ASR, appropriately trained LLM (pilot data), TTS;
- tools for measuring the relevant metrics

Evaluation procedure:

- Tested roles: end user (care provider)
- A team member with end user role will be reading out to a microphone ahead written queries and respond appropriately to the generated system outputs.

Second evaluation/demo (draft):

Operational environment:

- Inputs to the system: Spoken queries, level of difficulty: complex (metric: TBD, WP1), e.g., such that FCR response is needed
- System outputs: system responses on the GUI, continuous dialogue summary, continuous call priority
- Infrastructure: as in Section 2.4.3.

System toolset:

- Interactive Playground (IP), ASR, appropriately trained LLM (pilot data), TTS, Factual Information Retrieval (FIR), Call priority (optionally)
- Tools for measuring the relevant metrics

Evaluation procedure:

- Tested roles: technical staff, end user (care provider)

- A team member with technical staff role will first open the IP, selecting the relevant LLM, upon which the system will be appropriately configured.
- A team member with end user role will open the GUI; he/she will be reading out to a microphone ahead written queries and respond appropriately to the generated system outputs. Some of the queries and/or responses will be such that external information retrieval is necessary. During the dialogue, the system will be continuously outputting the call summary as well as the call priority. The content of the query will be designed so that the call priority reaches the highest value upon which the system announces that the call will be transferred to a human.

2.4.6 Activities related to stakeholder engagement

In the UNS pilot, we have established communication with external medical experts who assist us in designing the corpus content. With their expertise, we have identified various stakeholders who may be interested in our pilot project. Our targeted audience comprises medical staff working in medical call centres, including emergency call centres, and representatives of the technical and business communities (e.g. LLM developers and language technology providers). Our use case was presented to the stakeholders during the hybrid workshop, which was organised as part of the third plenary meeting hosted in Novi Sad, Serbia. During the workshop, stakeholders were actively involved in the decision-making process and their opinions were considered in the final decisions. Stakeholders will be kept informed about the progress, outcomes and any changes to our pilot through the ELOQUENCE website. Following the conclusion of the workshop, annual meetings with the stakeholders will be organised. Within the workshop, several questions were posed to the audience.

Questions for the audience

We propose to ask the audience the following questions:

- What features or capabilities do you believe are essential for the AI assistant described in the introduction?
- What potential benefits do you foresee with the implementation of such an AI assistant in a medical call centre?
- What feedback mechanisms should be in place for continuous improvement of this AI assistant?
- What is the best way to keep you informed about the progress and updates regarding the project pilot?

The preliminary analysis of the responses collected during the workshop, highlights the need for the AI assistant to excel in smart triage, effectively determining call urgency while accommodating Serbian-language interactions. Features like instant call summaries and clear question flow ensure that human agents can intervene quickly and with relevant context. Simple, visually intuitive tools are also valued to help agents grasp critical information at a glance, improving overall efficiency and clarity. The anticipated benefits include reduced wait times as the AI initiates information gathering immediately, ensuring faster and more consistent support for callers. Prioritizing urgent cases enhances service in rural or busy areas, while real-time assistance builds trust, particularly for parents in distress. Stakeholders also emphasized the importance of continuous improvement, suggesting mechanisms like operator feedback surveys, tracking triage metrics, and regular updates from medical staff to refine the system's functionality and responsiveness. More details will be provided in the next Deliverable of WP5.

2.4.7 Generalisation capabilities

The system to be developed in the UNS pilot is specifically focused on call centres for new parents, designing virtual assistants (VAs) to act as appropriate support for the corresponding medical staff. The assistants will be trained to interact with the end user (parent/child caregiver) by carrying out a question-driven dialogue to efficiently collect relevant data pertaining to the inquiry and providing an informative summary for the medical expert (e.g. a nurse) once he/she is able to take the call. In certain cases, and when appropriate, the VA will point the user towards the relevant information certified by the expert medical staff. Even though the application domain is specific and

focused, the described design of VAs exhibits strong generalisation capabilities: on a high level, the idea is to develop VAs that are trained to effectively identify the problem in question by interacting with the end user, and in certain cases, pointing the user towards the certified information that may help with resolving their query. For example, with appropriate retraining on the relevant data, the system of the UNS pilot could be adapted to call centres for elderly care, or medical emergencies, and in more distant application domains as well such as police and firefighters call centres, etc. With respect to different end user categories, aside from the targeted end users, the system could be used by students and trainees in the relevant domains as a means to acquire and test their knowledge, and potentially experts as well in certain specific cases (situations), such as in complementary domains - e.g., a firefighter seeking advice on how to provide emergency medical assistance (e.g., by browsing through a digital emergency handbook/similar, guided by the user information at hand, and quickly finding relevant information).

Generalisation categories	
End users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Parents and caregivers, medical students and trainees, medical experts ● End users, students, trainees and experts in other application domains (see below)
Business cases	TBD
Application domains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Medical assistance call centres: call centres for new parents, call centres for elderly care ● Emergency call centres: medical emergency, police, firefighters ● Information-providing call centres: weather information services, public offices

3 Usability framework for ELOQUENCE assessment

The Usability Evaluation Framework describes the metrics and procedures for evaluating the ELOQUENCE output in both safety-critical contact centres, smart homes and social scenarios considered by the pilots. The goal is to analyse the ELOQUENCE tools within the different use cases and assess both user acceptance and usability, thereby offering valuable insights to guide the ongoing redesign and optimization of the different tools and components provided by the different WPs.

The plan is defined by considering:

- KRs related to the WP5 and to the Objective 4: Definition of a framework to assess the conversational AI methods in various scenarios (KR-11, KR-12, KR-13, KR-14, KR-15).
- KRs related to the WP5 and to the Objective 5: *Definition and execution of pilots to validate ELOQUENCE technologies* (KR-16, KR-17, KR-18).

This Section outlines the **criteria**, **metrics**, and **KPIs** for evaluating the ELOQUENCE project in the different demonstrative use cases implemented by the pilots. The framework is essential to establish **methodologies** and **guidelines** to drive the assessment of the ELOQUENCE technology in terms of feasibility and potential impact. The evaluation expects to involve productive iterations with the WP1 and WP6. It aims at gathering and providing feedback and seeking to achieve both continuous technological improvements, e.g. metrics, and social and ethical dialogue, with respect to ethical aspects, e.g. related to the previous technical developments, the employed data, tools used, and people involved in the pilots.

The evaluation framework defined in this Section aims to understand whether an **agent or virtual assistant** based on ELOQUENCE technologies can solve complex real-world tasks. For this reason, for the usability evaluation of the ELOQUENCE technologies in real scenarios, the activities are focused more on the agent's capabilities, assessing how they emerge from the LLM's core abilities.

Criteria, metrics and KPIs will be considered according to real users' intended to use the LLM-based assistant. Recent works have proposed benchmarking LLMs also from a user perspective to understand how the LLMs satisfy users' actual intents and needs as described in (Peng, et al., 2024), (Wang, Ma, Sun, Zhang, & Nie, 2024) and (Wang, et al., 2024). In line with this approach, the demonstration and evaluation activities conducted throughout the 4 pilots will be driven by **human expectations** about the **role and abilities** of LLMs in the task accomplishment and the interaction in the scenarios of interest.

It is crucial to gather **users' feedback** to evaluate their perceived usefulness and usability of the ELOQUENCE tools. This feedback serves as an indirect measure of user **satisfaction** after interacting with the products. The key is to understand how effectively ELOQUENCE products meet user expectations in specific contexts, rather than simply assessing isolated, decontextualized capabilities of the models.

The following sections provide detailed information for each pilot:

- **Pilot Overview:** a description of how the specific components, datasets, criteria, metrics, and KPIs are defined and applied for each pilot. It highlights connections with other WPs to ensure alignment with the overall project objectives.
- **Criteria:** an outline of the specific conditions or requirements that must be satisfied for the pilot outcomes to be deemed valid, incorporating criteria related to technologies from WP1-4 and, additional criteria unique to the pilot's implementation and following the ethical considerations from WP6.
- **Metrics:** the quantifiable measures that will be used to evaluate the performance and progress of the pilot, including metrics defined in WP1-4, potentially adapted for the specific case study and, (if applicable), ad-hoc metrics defined specifically for the pilot.
- **KPIs:** the thresholds or benchmarks linked to the metrics, that will be considered to determine whether a criterion has been met.

3.1 Pilot 1: “Privacy-preserving language model learning through decentralised training in smart homes”

3.1.1 Summary

As explained in Section 2.1, the goal of pilot 1 is to demonstrate domain adaptation and privacy-preserving techniques for domestic applications. Specifically, the pilot 1 develops a decentralized and distributed federated learning framework for fine-tuning language and speech models between a cloud server (e.g., Barcelona Supercomputing Centre - BSC) and end-users, such as partner institutions. Additionally, a CLI or simple API will be provided to the ELOQUENCE consortium, enabling the federation of LLM and speech models from different clients/partners with the cloud provider. This federation will support both hierarchical and asynchronous learning, thus helping on bolstering the **KR3 – Adaptation of LLMs**.

Ultimately, by employing the technology developed by other WPs of the project and our framework, we aim to showcase an adapted to domestic environment, conversational and context-aware virtual agent that leverages LLM and ASR technologies trained from several heterogenous clients and data. We will showcase how the framework performs using our conversational-based ELOQUENCE evaluation dataset, see Section 2.1.3. By doing so, the contribution will align with the **KR17** regarding the **demonstration of a virtual agent for home scenario**.

To effectively monitor the progress and performance of the pilot, we have established a set of criteria that the pilot must meet, accompanied by their corresponding metrics. These metrics are designed to evaluate three key components: the FL training process, the privacy protection layer, and the in-house ELOQUENCE dataset.

3.1.2 Pilot Overview

A systematic summary of the main components is provided in Table 9, along with the assessment criteria and related metrics for each. The FL training process, the additional privacy layer, and the domestic domain comprise the pilot’s primary components. The criteria set the conditions pilot’s components must satisfy, while the metrics specify all the pertinent measurements, including those directly related to the criteria and to the essential tools and technologies required for demonstrating in a home environment.

Table 9 Overview of Pilot 1 Criteria and Metrics

COMPONENT	Distributed Federated Learning Architecture	Command Line Interface (CLI)	Additional Privacy Layer	Domestic Domain
CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy • Efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding • Factual Information Retrieval
METRICS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training time • Training, validation and test loss (aggregated and per client) • Number of trainable parameters • Communication Bandwidth • Downstream tasks metrics (see domestic domain) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy configurable • Selection of optimization algorithms • Selection of privacy Tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Epsilon (ϵ) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precision • Recall • F1-score • ROGUE • WER

3.1.3 Criteria

Criteria specifically related to the Distributed Federated Learning Architecture

- **Privacy:** The system should successfully train/FT a fundamental model using a decentralized and distributed federated learning approach that avoids direct data sharing among peers. This can involve sharing partly

the clients' model weights or specific layers with the cloud (e.g., BSC) while keeping personal data private and stored locally on the clients' devices -- e.g., local data from partners or homes in their local databases. Given a training system functions correctly with a FL framework, it directly satisfies the privacy criteria.

- **Efficiency:** The system should train/FT a fundamental model in a computationally efficient manner, focusing on training time efficiency, model efficiency, and resource utilization. Achieving this efficiency involves applying techniques to reduce both the training time and the number of parameter operations, as well as parallelizing the computational tasks, in comparison to its baseline version (i.e., naive base model), without significantly compromising its performance.

Criteria focused on the Command Line Interface

- **Usability:** The framework should be user-friendly to the ELOQUENCE's consortium allowing the federation of LLM and speech models from different clients/partners and the cloud server, BSC.
- **Flexibility:** The framework should support customizable settings, enabling flexibility in client/server configurations and privacy-preserving methods.

Criteria focused on the Additional Privacy Layer

- **Privacy:** The privacy module should enhance the protection of clients' local data throughout the FL training process, ensuring robust privacy measures.

Criteria focused on the Domestic Domain

- **Understanding:** The AI assistant should precisely comprehend real-world situations, their context, and unstructured dialogues, as those found in domestic settings; relating to activities conducted at home or within family relationships, ensuring its suitability for assessing the intended use case, e.g. activity summarization or information retrieval.
- **Factual Information Retrieval:** Since home virtual assistants are intended for providing relevant and accurate information in response to user queries, they should demonstrate high-quality information retrieval capabilities. This involves retrieving the most pertinent and contextually appropriate information from a wide range of sources. It is essential for the AI assistant to understand the nuances of natural language, interpret user intent, and retrieve information that aligns with the user's needs.

3.1.4 Metrics

Metrics focused on the Distributed Federated Learning Architecture

The primary criterion for deeming the FL architecture framework successful is its ability to perform fully functional, decentralized and distributed training and fine-tuning of AI models, like as LLMs and ASRs. In the context of the FL framework, this approach guarantees the preservation of clients' privacy, such as through the partial sharing of local model parameters or layers with a cloud server.

To effectively monitor the progress and performance of the FL architecture development, we will use the following metrics:

- **Training time:** Measures the duration of the entire training process, providing insight into computational efficiency with respect to a fully parameter training or FT of a foundational model.
- **Training, validation and test losses (aggregated and per client):** Tracks the models' performance during the whole training process, giving insight into the capacity to converge of the models.
- **Number of trainable parameters:** Indicates the proportion of model parameters that are actively optimized during training, relevant for efficiency and resource usage.

These metrics give a comprehensive overview of the entire FL training system, enabling users to evaluate its efficiency, scalability and privacy-preserving capabilities effectively.

Metrics focused on the Command Line Interface

The Federated Learning (FL) framework must offer flexibility, allowing for easy configuration via configuration files, such as XML, YAML, or JSON. This enables users to adjust and tailor the system according to their specific requirements and preferences. The FL configurations should provide a robust and comprehensive set of options for users to select from, including but not limited to:

- Selection of Optimization Algorithms
- Selection of Privacy Tools
- Customization of Hyperparameters

Metrics focused on the Additional Privacy Layer

To evaluate the privacy performance of our additional component, we will employ differential privacy metrics that quantify the level of protection achieved by adding noise to the data. Specifically, we will measure epsilon (ϵ), a key parameter that represents the strength of the privacy guarantees provided by differential privacy algorithms. A smaller epsilon value indicates stronger privacy, reflecting a higher level of noise and less risk of revealing sensitive information. We will explore on the trade-off between ϵ and accuracy relationship.

Metrics focused on the domestic domain

To showcase our pilot in smart home scenarios using the personalized, conversational, and context-aware virtual agent, we will use the ELOQUENCE dataset introduced in Section 2.1.3. This test set will enable us to evaluate the performance of an AI agent in different tasks by calculating various accuracy-oriented metrics in both text and speech modalities. Below is a table outlining the different tasks and their corresponding metrics (Table 10).

Table 10 Pilot 1 metrics explanation

Task	Metric	Explanation
Factual Information Retrieval	Precision	Measures the fraction of retrieved information that is relevant to the user query.
	Recall	Measures the fraction of relevant information that is successfully retrieved.
	F1-score	Harmonic mean of precision and recall.
NER	Precision	Measures the ratio of correctly identified named entities to the total entities identified by the model.
	Recall	Measures the ratio of correctly identified named entities to the total entities present in the ground truth.
	F1-score	Harmonic mean of precision and recall.
Summarization	ROGUE (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation)	Measures content overlap between the reference of the test set and the output generated by the model, with an emphasis on recall (i.e., how much of the reference response is accurately captured in the generated output).
Transcription	WER (Word Error Rate)	Measures the difference between the transcribed output of the ASR system and the reference transcription based on number of substitutions, deletions, insertion and the total number of words in the reference transcription.

Speaker diarization ³	DER (Diarization Error Rate)	Measures the fraction of time that is not attributed correctly to a speaker or to non-speech, including errors from missed speech, false alarms, and speaker confusion
	SER (Speaker Error Rate)	Measures the proportion of speaker assignment errors, excluding non-speech segments.

3.1.5 KPIs

Based on the KR3 and KR17, we aim to achieve the following qualitative and quantitative KPIs by the end of the pilot development, thereby ensuring a privacy-preserving model training approach:

Qualitative KPIs:

- Deploy an architecture for **decentralized and distributed training**.
- Deploy an architecture for **ensuring privacy of user’s data**.
- **Leverage a CLI** based interface to the consortium partners providing access to the previous architecture.
- Integrate **mechanisms to bolster data privacy** and ensure strong privacy guarantees depending on the end-user’s trade-off.

Quantitative KPIs:

- **Reduction of at least 90% in Communication Bandwidth:** Significantly reduce the bandwidth required for communication between the cloud and each client during each FL training round with respect to a naive FL implementation that transmits full model updates without compression or optimization.
- **Reduction of at least 50% in Training Time:** Decrease the overall time needed to train the models with respect a regular baseline training setup.
- **Maintenance of Performance Quality:** Accomplish the above reductions while maintaining models’ performance quality with a **maximum allowable degradation of 10%**. Performance will be assessed:
 - Using the metrics in Section 3.1.4.
 - Using the Alpaca and ELOQUENCE test sets, detailed in previous sections.

³ Speaker diarization, while not a target technology by the ELOQUENCE project, still plays a significant role in spoken dialogues. The Pilot 1 will incorporate reporting error metrics on an integrated diarization tool, which allows for the analysis of the system’s performance and identification of areas for improvement.

3.2 Pilot 2: “Social context-aware language model detecting biases”

3.2.1 Summary

The aim of the pilot is the assessment of ELOQUENCE technologies in social scenarios, focusing on the agent’s ability to handle dialogues in a socially appropriate and bias-free manner. Pilot 2 is related to **KR18: Demonstrate virtual agents in social situations** and evaluate possible biases exhibition. To reach these outcomes, a conversational, advisor agent is built on top of the LLMs technologies developed by WP1-4.

The agent is equipped with baseline knowledge enabling it to manage the dialogue according to a specific conversational practice. Specifically, we consider a counselling practice (i.e. career advice, university programs), where a virtual advisory agent provides personalized assistance to users according to their profiles. The choice of this use case is motivated by the recognition that factors such as culture, gender, religion, and ethnicity can influence biases in the responses generated by the agent.

To implement the pilot, a conversational agent is built on top of the ELOQUENCE technology, integrating a Knowledge Base (KB) that combines both domain-specific information and a knowledge grounded on a model based on social practices theory, that allows the agent to manage the typical dialogue flow associated with the practice being examined. It allows the agent to proactively collect necessary data to profile users and provide the best advice based on its understanding of the domain, user interests, and current conversation.

Since the goal is to uncover existing biases in the underlying language model, the conversation should steer towards the natural emergence of situations in where they may arise. For this reason, in formalizing the agent's knowledge base and reasoning processes, any explicit modelling of information related to social biases will be avoided. This ensures that the biases naturally emerge from the language model and are not artificially avoided or reinforced. Based on the results of the pilot, conclusions can then be drawn to inform procedures for biases mitigation.

To analyse whether the generated conversations reveal biases rooted in social factors, prompt engineering and bias stimulation strategies are used to test the agent’s responses.

The pilot relies on open datasets and/or synthetic dialogues with synthetic individuals, generated according to personas methodology, to elicit biases that might not appear with real user samples.

3.2.2 Pilot Overview

Table 11 provides a structured overview of the key components of pilot 2, reporting the evaluation criteria and corresponding metrics for each of them. The table is organized into four main components: the Synthetic Personas Dataset, Baseline Knowledge Dataset, Conversational Agent, and Social Bias Detection system. For each component, we have identified specific evaluation criteria. Just to provide an example, we identified reliability for the datasets and credibility for the conversational agent. Then we supported these criteria with concrete and measurable metrics. These metrics range from demographic representation in the datasets to conversation quality assessment and qualitative analysis of robustness in bias detection. The following subsections detail all the identified criteria and metrics.

Table 11 Overview of pilot 2 Criteria and Metrics

COMPONENT	Synthetic Personas Dataset	Baseline Knowledge Dataset	Conversation Agent	Social Bias Detection
CRITERIA	Reliability	Reliability	Credibility (Coherence, Intent Understanding, Social Ability)	Robustness (Fairness, Relevance, Consistency)
METRICS	Gender Representation	Geographical Distribution	Similarity to a real conversation	Pairwise Comparison Metric (PCM)

	Geographical Distribution Socioeconomic Diversity Racial/Ethnic Representation	Field of Study balance	KSVear	Background Comparison Metric (BCM) Style and Content Analysis
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3.2.3 Criteria

The criteria outlined below are grouped based on their relevance to the specific characteristics required for the pilot implementation and their connection to the technologies developed in WP1-4 (see Table 11).

Criteria specifically related to the Pilot Instantiation

- **Reliability of Synthetic Personas:** The agent should be assessed using a varied sample of individuals. The criterion is to use a synthetic dataset that represents a wide range of demographic characteristics, ensuring the agent's effectiveness across different social contexts and enabling a comprehensive evaluation of potential biases in its interactions.
- **User-sample Representativeness:** When the agent interacts directly with real users, we must ensure that the sample is selected based on representativeness criteria: geographic origin, cultural background, and gender must be equally distributed to avoid implicit biases.
- **Baseline Knowledge Construction:** The baseline knowledge is selected/constructed by crawling the university websites. The collected data must be reliable and represent coherently the distribution of universities in the territory. In addition, the selection must be balanced between STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) and humanities studies.

Criteria related to ELOQUENCE technologies

- **Credibility of the Conversational Agent:** The agent must be able to credibly manage a conversational practice typical of a social context. It must be capable of engaging in socially believable conversations and handling typical social practices in a natural and coherent manner. It must be perceived as socially credible by a significant portion of users or evaluators.
 - **Coherence:** The answers produced, and questions made to collect information are exclusively related to the scope of the conversation.
 - **Intent Understanding:** The practice proposed in the scenario has no unique development; the agent understands the intent and plans the dialogue.
 - **Social Ability:** The agent must be able to manage a conversational practice typical of a social context.
- **Robustness of Social Biases Detection:** It is crucial to develop a methodology that allows the identification of social biases present in the used LLM. The methodology developed must accurately identify and measure social biases present in the language model, to understand if the technology ensures:
 - **Fairness:** The suggestions provided by the system (agent) should not favour or disadvantage any particular social group.
 - **Relevance:** Advice should align with the user profile (for example, interests and qualifications), which are explicitly declared or collected in the dialogue.
 - **Consistency:** Multiple reiterations of the system using similar user profiles should produce similar types of suggestions.

3.2.4 Metrics

We consider both qualitative and quantitative metrics, distinguishing between user-driven data and automated system-generated data. Also in this case, metrics are outlined with respect to the main aspects characterizing the pilot.

Metrics focused on synthetic personas

- Gender Representation: average percentage of male and female personas within the dataset/real users' sample.
- Geographical Distribution: the variety of geographical regions represented in the dataset/real users' sample.
- Socioeconomic Diversity: range of socioeconomic statuses represented within the persona dataset/real users' sample.
- Racial/Ethnic Representation: distribution of racial and ethnic groups within the persona dataset/real users' sample.

Metrics for Baseline Knowledge Construction

- Geographical Distribution: distribution of universities in the territory.
- Field of Study balance: number of departments focused on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) and humanities studies.

Metrics for Conversational Agent

- User's perception of generated dialogues: the generated synthetic dialogues will first be evaluated through the Dialog2Flow tool (Burdisso, Madikeri, & Motliceck, 2024) to verify that the generated dialogue flow is as close as possible to the flow of a real conversation, and then involving some volunteers to assess how well the agent performs in the eyes of humans.
- Qualitative evaluation: the questionnaire KSVear (presented in Annex 6.1) will be used to collect the user point of view of the agent's behaviour compared with the expectations of a real user, regarding the understanding of user intents, a correct behaviour with respect to societal values and norms within the situation, the ability in providing advice or action recommendations relevant to the given situation. Care should be taken in selecting a representative sample of subjects to be involved in the test.

Metrics for detecting social biases

A Bias Index aggregates the scores from various bias-related metrics (Related to Metrics in D1.1, Section 3.3.1). The different metrics will be implemented considering that social biases are highly context dependent. This involves ensuring fairness in treatment among social groups that differ in protected attributes but are similar regarding profile attributes (i.e. user preferences, needs, personality traits) which influence how advice should be tailored to individuals in specific situations.

Possible metrics, identified according to the literature (Czarnowska, Yogarshi, & Kashif, 2021) (Gallegos, et al., 2024) are the following:

- Pairwise Comparison Metric (PCM): based on a ground truth dataset, context dependent.
- Background Comparison Metric (BCM): based on a ground truth dataset, context dependent.
- Style and Content Analysis: to identify representational harms and ensure fair communication, based on linguistic resources.
 - Term-Based Metric: Analyse the usage of potentially negative or stereotypical terms.
 - Sentiment-Based Metric: Evaluate the sentiment in advice to ensure equitable treatment.
 - Form Analysis: Examine the structure of responses, including speech acts used.

3.2.5 KPI

The following Key Performance Indicators have been considered as references to enhance the performance of the pilot in terms of bias detection, the agent's social credibility, and task's usability. These KPIs are derived from the outlined metrics, specifically those related to assessing the agent's ability to manage social contexts and ensure fair interactions.

1. **Accuracy in Bias Detection:** Achieve at least an 85% accuracy rate in detecting social biases within the agent's conversations. This will be measured using the Bias Index, which aggregates scores from the various bias-related metrics (e.g., Pairwise Comparison Metric, Background Comparison Metric, Term-Based Metric). A ground truth dataset, consisting of annotated synthetic conversations, will serve as a reference.
2. **Social Credibility:** The agent should be evaluated at least as 90% socially credible, based on participant feedback using the KSVear questionnaire (details are reported in Appendix 6.1).
3. **Usability:** Achieve an agent usability score of at least 80% in the pilot task accomplishment. This will evaluate how effectively users can interact with the agent, complete tasks, and achieve their objectives during the pilot phase. This will be measured through the modality proposed in the usability evaluation section (paragraph 3.5).

These KPIs will be reviewed over time and used as indicators of the success of ELOQUENCE output.

3.3 Pilot 3: *“Retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, capable of understanding the user's goals, making API calls and respond with empathy”*

3.3.1 Summary

This pilot aims to thoroughly assess the effectiveness and abilities of our innovative virtual agent, powered by LLM technology, in the challenging field of customer service. Our main goal is to create and train an advanced virtual assistant using a wide range of enterprise-specific conversational data. This data will come from various sectors, including complex financial services, insurance, and essential utilities. By training the virtual agent on this diverse dataset, we intend to develop a versatile assistant capable of applying its knowledge and skills to new businesses without requiring additional customization with company-specific information. To support its functions, the virtual agent will have access to both structured and semi-structured documentation for each company it serves. This access is essential, as it allows the agent to efficiently find and intelligently apply relevant information when responding to the diverse and often intricate inquiries from callers.

For adapting/tuning the trainable components, such as the retrieval mechanism, we will develop datasets that closely mimic real-world interactions between users and enterprise agents on the Omilia platform. These datasets will also incorporate enterprise-specific documentation, similar to that used by actual businesses, which is essential for training the retrieval mechanism. Additionally, Omilia's Quality Assurance department will design all test cases, ensuring they encompass the complex dialogue patterns typically found in genuine conversations between callers and human agents.

The major research efforts will be targeted towards:

1. LLMs enhanced with advanced retrieval mechanisms, exhibiting the capacity to dynamically integrate and utilize enterprise-specific information without necessitating the computationally intensive process of fine-tuning. These models demonstrate adaptive capabilities that allow for seamless incorporation of novel organizational contexts.
2. Refined LLMs equipped with meta-learning capabilities, enabling them to autonomously discern the appropriate circumstances and methodologies for leveraging external tools and web services. These models possess the ability to strategically employ such resources in service of achieving the end-user's specified objectives with optimal efficiency.
3. Hybrid LLMs that synergistically combine domain-specific knowledge pertinent to individual enterprises with the vast corpus of information acquired during the pretraining phase. These models are engineered

to generate responses that not only accurately address the caller's inquiries but also exhibit a degree of emotional intelligence and empathetic understanding, thus enhancing the overall quality of human-AI interactions.

3.3.2 Pilot Overview

A concise schematic overview of the pilot's potential criteria, metrics and KPIs is presented in Table 12.

Table 12 Criteria, metrics and KPIs for Pilot 3

Criteria	Module	Metrics	KPI	
extracting factual data	RAG	Precision	—	
		Recall	—	
delivering grounded information		Mean Average Precision (MAP)	—	
		Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG)	—	
multi-domain		Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR)	—	
		Context Utilization	—	
		Query-Document-Answer Alignment	—	
dialog-state tracking		Call Centre	Average Handle Time (AHT)	
			First Call Resolution (FCR)	20% increase
			Call Containment Rate (CCR)	20% increase
	Call Abandonment Rate		—	
natural language processing	Average Speed of Answer (ASA)		—	
	Transfer Rate		—	
	Intent Recognition Accuracy		—	
	Entity Extraction Accuracy		—	
natural language understanding	Sentiment Analysis Accuracy		—	
	Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI)		—	
	Satisfaction Feedback (SF)	—		
	Net Promoter Score (NPS)	—		
API calls/agent escalation	Self-Service Rate	—		
	Agent Utilization	—		
	Task Success Rate	—		
	Average Task Completion Time	—		

multi-modal	Task Abandonment Rate	—
	Uptime	—
	Response Time	—
	Error Rate	—
	Scalability	—

3.3.3 Criteria

The main challenges and effectively the specifications and requirements that must be met for the pilot's outcome to be considered successful are the following:

1. Extracting factual data, particularly from unstructured enterprise-specific knowledge, and modifying its semantic recognition components (such as intents and slots) and conversation flow without requiring fine-tuning on company-specific datasets.
2. Determining the appropriate timing for API calls to web services or human agent escalation and identifying the necessary information fields to be completed beforehand.
3. Delivering information to callers that is firmly rooted in the enterprise's documentation, avoiding fabricated or hallucinated responses.
4. Demonstrating superior natural language understanding and dialog-state tracking by comprehending implicit user responses (pragmatic inference), consolidating intents, and recognizing key entities across multiple conversation steps.
5. Functioning effectively across various communication channels (voice and text), multiple languages, and diverse subject areas.
6. Perceiving the caller's emotional state and adapting responses, accordingly, eliminating the need for explicit definition of emotion recognition units and corresponding reaction patterns.

As can be seen the underlying denominator of these requirements involves RAG mechanisms and automated call centre technologies. These introduce a gamut of pilot-specific (as well as cross-pilot) criteria that need to be monitored via a corresponding range of metrics.

3.3.4 Metrics

RAG metrics:

1. Precision: The proportion of relevant documents in the top-k retrieved results
2. Recall: The proportion of all relevant documents that are retrieved in the top-k results
3. Mean Average Precision (MAP): Average of precision values at different recall levels
4. Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain (nDCG): Measures the ranking quality of retrieved documents
5. Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR): The average of reciprocal ranks of the first relevant document
6. Context Utilization: How effectively the generator uses the retrieved context
7. Query-Document-Answer Alignment: Consistency across the query, retrieved documents, and generated answer

Automated Call Centre metrics:

1. Average Handle Time (AHT): The average duration of a call, including talk time, hold time, and after-call work
2. First Call Resolution (FCR): Percentage of calls resolved during the first try without the need for a follow-up
3. Call Containment Rate (CCR): Percentage of calls that are successfully resolved within an automated system
4. Call Abandonment Rate: Percentage of callers who hang up before reaching an agent or completing their interaction

5. Average Speed of Answer (ASA): Average time callers wait before their call is answered
6. Transfer Rate: Percentage of calls transferred to a human agent or another department
7. Intent Recognition Accuracy: How accurately the system identifies customer intents
8. Entity Extraction Accuracy: Precision in identifying specific entities (e.g., names, dates) in customer speech
9. Sentiment Analysis Accuracy: Correctness in detecting customer emotions and sentiments
10. Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI): Average of post-call surveys or follow-up interactions with customers
11. Satisfaction Feedback (SF): Direct feedback from customers on their experience
12. Net Promoter Score (NPS): Likelihood of customers recommending the service
13. Self-Service Rate: Percentage of inquiries resolved without human intervention
14. Agent Utilization: How effectively human agents are used in conjunction with the automated system
15. Task Success Rate: Percentage of customer tasks successfully completed
16. Average Task Completion Time: Time taken to complete common tasks
17. Task Abandonment Rate: Percentage of tasks abandoned before completion
18. Uptime: Percentage of time the automated system is operational
19. Response Time: How quickly the system responds to user inputs
20. Error Rate: Frequency of system errors or failures
21. Scalability: Ability to handle increased call volumes without performance degradation

Further details on certain of these criteria which are explicitly employed in KRs are provided next:

FCR measures the percentage of customer calls or inquiries that are fully resolved during the initial contact, without the need for follow-up interactions or escalations. It's calculated as follows:

$$\text{FCR} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of calls resolved on first contact}}{\text{Total number of calls}} \right) * 100$$

To calculate this for a given day: (a) count the total number of calls received that day, (b) determine how many of those calls were completely resolved during the initial interaction.

CCR refers to the percentage of calls that are successfully resolved or "contained" within an automated system without requiring intervention from a human agent. It is calculated in the following way:

$$\text{CCR} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of calls resolved through automated systems}}{\text{Total number of calls received}} \right) * 100$$

To calculate this for a given day: (a) count the total number of calls received that day, (b) determine how many of those calls were fully resolved by the automated system.

SF measured through summaries provided by users (e.g. at the end of a call) is a valuable method for assessing customer satisfaction and gathering insights about the quality of service or product. Usually, it is conducted at the end of an interaction and can be in the form of a short survey or a few targeted questions. Often uses rating scales along with open-ended comments.

CSI is an objective and versatile analytical tool used to measure and track customer satisfaction. CSI is typically measured through post-call surveys or follow-up interactions with customers by taking the average of all customer satisfaction ratings over a specific period.

Nevertheless, it is important to note that, given the nascent state of the pilot study's developmental trajectory, the associated evaluative criteria and quantitative metrics remain in a state of continuous investigation. As the research progresses and more empirical data is accumulated, a process of iterative refinement will be employed to identify and implement the most appropriate and statistically robust assessment parameters. This adaptive approach will ensure that the long-term analytical framework is optimized for maximum validity and reliability.

3.3.5 KPI

Overall, from a macroscopic perspective, the principal qualitative KPI is going to be the demonstration of a fully functional virtual agent capable of meeting users' needs, of invoking automatically API calls and enriching its verbal responses with empathy. The RAG capabilities that will be incorporated are anticipated to play a crucial role in the development and optimization of high-performance, personalized LLMs. The effectiveness of these models will be rigorously evaluated through the definition and execution of a comprehensive suite of test cases and application scenarios, as delineated in the project's **KR16, KR17, and KR18**.

Furthermore, **KRs 11 through 15** will serve as the foundation for a comprehensive qualitative assessment of the developed LLM technologies. It is crucial to emphasize that the findings and contributions derived from pilot study 3 -whether in the context of the more narrowly defined customer service domain or within the broader spectrum of application scenarios across all pilots- will undergo a two-phase evaluation protocol. In Phase I, baseline performance metrics will be established using unmodified, pre-trained LLMs. Phase II will involve the evaluation of implemented LLM methodologies, like for instance the branched RAG approach. Comparative analysis between these phases will be conducted to quantify relative performance differentials. The primary objective of this procedure is two-fold: (a) to develop LLMs with enhanced efficiency and functional capabilities, and (b) to empirically demonstrate performance improvements through project-defined KPIs. This approach enables both qualitative and quantitative assessment of the implemented methodologies' efficacy in advancing LLM performance. More specifically, with respect to the KRs under examination for WP5, the quantitative benchmarks for performance are as follows:

- First Call Resolution (FCR) → 20% increase
- Call Containment Rate (CCR) → 20% increase

3.4 Pilot 4: *“Upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues”*

3.4.1 Summary

This pilot focuses on enhancing the efficiency of safety-critical medical call centres by integrating AI-based assistant systems to assist medical staff. The primary objective is to reduce the workload of junior medical personnel while maintaining their control over decision-making. The pilot will simulate real-world call centre environments offering advice to new parents on handling situations with newborns.

A multimodal audio corpus of 150 unstructured dialogues will be developed, including both general and emergency scenarios. Data collection will be facilitated through a staged recording process with callers represented by natural speakers and service providers by a mix of natural speakers and text-to-speech (TTS) systems. Dialogue annotations will include acted emotional content, context, and categorized enquiry types based on pre-designed ontologies.

The AI system will summarise potential solutions and provide relevant information to medical staff, rather than recommending solutions directly to callers. This approach aims to improve service quality while reducing operational workload on medical personnel. UNS, as the data owner, will leverage its expertise to data collection frameworks for this initiative.

UNS as a data provider and the pilot owner will create an annotated corpus that supports AI-driven call centre assistance systems, incorporating TTS-enabled inquiry capture for initial caller handling.

3.4.2 Pilot Overview

The pilot integrates several ELOQUENCE components to enhance the efficiency of medical call centres. Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) converts caller speech into text, facilitating seamless interaction with downstream systems, while Text-to-Speech (TTS) provides synthesized responses during initial handling stages or automated interactions, ensuring clear and consistent communication. A LLM drives dialogue management by interpreting user queries, understanding context, and generating relevant information for medical staff. An Information Retrieval system extracts relevant medical advice and best practices from a comprehensive database, enabling junior personnel to make informed decisions efficiently. Call Priority Estimation leverages speech tone, urgency, and content analysis to prioritize calls, ensuring critical cases receive immediate attention. Additionally, a Text Summarization condenses lengthy call transcripts into concise summaries, aiding staff in record-keeping and follow-up actions. These components are orchestrated through a centralized system that ensures seamless integration and optimal performance across the entire workflow, aligning with the pilot's objective of reducing workload while maintaining high service quality. These tools will be developed within the WP2. A set of dialogues will be recorded within a staged recording process, annotated and submitted. Staged recording process will be done in a close cooperation with the junior medical personnel.

The overview of main components of the system and system as a whole with corresponding criteria and metrics is given in Table 13.

Table 13 Overview of pilot 4 Criteria and Metrics

	Dataset	Dialogue summarization	Dialogue manager	CALL CENTER
CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of summarization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> User satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reducing time responses
METRIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of dialogues Average turns per dialogue Topics covered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ROUGE BertScore 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informativeness (MOS scale) User experience (MOS scale) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average wait times (nominal calls, prioritized calls) Information extraction time

3.4.3 Criteria

This section will give the description of the criteria used for the performance of the call centres. Currently, call centres, due to the limited number of available visiting nurses at any given time, operate as follows: When a parent contacts the visiting nurse service, if no nurse is currently available, the caller is placed on hold. Once a nurse becomes free, she takes the call based on a first-in, first-out system and begins the conversation with the caller. During the call, the caller explains the issue, the nurse asks the necessary questions to get a complete picture and then provides appropriate advice. The implementation of this pilot allows for the following scenario:

- The caller is immediately served by speaking with a voice-bot assistant, explaining the issue, and answering the bot's questions.
- Based on the collected information, the software prioritizes the urgency of each call for the visiting nurse.
- The visiting nurse receives a summary of the caller's conversation from the voice-bot, verifies the provided information during a brief conversation, and immediately gives advice.

Therefore, the success of this pilot project is measured by several aspects:

- The first aspect is **reducing the time before a caller begins to receive service**. The software with the voice bot can simultaneously assist multiple callers, whereas a nurse cannot.

- The second aspect is **decreasing wait times for urgent calls**. If the software successfully prioritizes calls, more urgent cases should have minimal wait times to connect with a nurse, regardless of the number and order of other callers in the queue.
- The third aspect involves **reducing the time a nurse spends with a single caller**. The nurse's role is limited to reviewing a summary of the problem provided by the voice bot, verifying the most critical information, and giving final advice, instead of fully listening to the caller's explanation and asking all necessary questions to get a complete picture.

Ultimately, the success of the pilot is reflected in the **number of calls a call centre with N visiting nurses can handle within a given time frame** when using a voice-bot.

Although the specific statistics for the mentioned metrics in current call centres and, for this particular case, are not available online, they can be gathered by contacting call centres directly or by similar statistics for call centres in general (available online), that can be used as a baseline to measure the success of the pilot project.

3.4.4 Metrics

As highlighted in deliverable D1.1 the metrics for evaluation of dialogue systems can be categorized into automatic and human evaluation. We plan to incorporate both types in the process of evaluating our system. Taking in account the architecture of our system the metrics used in our pilot could be divided into two groups:

- metrics related to dialogue management
- metrics related to user-experience

The metrics related to dialogue management are based on the automatic evaluation of the part of the system performing dialogue summarization. We will rely on well-known metrics for this type of task: BLEU (BiLingual Evaluation Understudy) and ROUGE (Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation) and BERTScore, which are also introduced in D1.1.

The core mechanism of BLEU involves computing the precision of n-grams generated by the model in comparison to n-grams extracted from a reference text. It assigns a score based on the overlap of these n-grams and includes a penalty for shorter outputs to ensure a more accurate assessment of text quality.

ROUGE is a metric designed specifically for evaluating text generation, particularly in automatic summarization tasks. Unlike BLEU, which focuses on precision by measuring n-gram overlap from the generated text to the reference, ROUGE emphasizes recall by assessing how many n-grams from the reference text appear in the generated output. Additionally, ROUGE extends its evaluation beyond n-grams to include individual word overlaps, allowing it to capture word-level similarities more effectively.

Unlike previously introduced metrics which focus on exact word matches or overlap, BERTScore leverages contextual embeddings from pre-trained language models, such as BERT, to assess semantic similarity between the generated text and the reference. It should be noted that there are several other model-based metrics (where models used are usually LLMs) but the usage of these metrics for our use case is limited by absence of well-trained LLMs for Serbian. On the other hand, there are some successful attempts in training BERT based model for Serbian and similar languages (Ljubešić, 2021) which makes BERTScore metrics applicable in our pilot.

Concerning the UNS use case, the interpretation of KR14 is formulated as: "Reduction in time needed for information collection/verification by human agent", as the closest to call containment due to data gathering. The metric associated with this key result will be interpreted as: "The time needed for human verification of the conversation summary provided by the system will be shorter than the time needed for the collection of the same information by the human agent from scratch."

The user-related metrics will be based on human evaluation. The evaluation should be carried out using appropriate questionnaires. The questionnaires evaluation strategy will be based on Likert scale (Joshi, 2015). i.e. using range of answers, most-likely, 5-point scale. We group these types of evaluation into three groups

Informational Effectiveness - Examines the system's ability to generate meaningful and actionable outputs for medical staff.

Informativeness: Determines whether all necessary information is extracted from the parent's input and reflected in the summary.

User Interaction Quality - Focuses on how well the system engages with and supports the user.

User experience: Captures the users' (parents and medical staff) feedback regarding their experience with the system.

3.4.5 KPI

We propose following KPI connected to evaluation metrics:

- ROUGE-1 score above 0.35 and ROUGE-2 above 0.15
- BERTScore F1 above 0.7

20% relative reduction in the time needed for human verification of the conversation summary provided by the system in comparison with the time needed for the collection of the same information by the human agent from scratch.

The user related metrics above 4.0

The proposed values are slightly lower compared to the best values found in literature. But it should be noted that values found in literature are mostly connected to databases and systems in English. Since there are almost non-existing LLMs and systems in Serbian (as it is resource scarce language) we suggest more conservative values.

There are also KPIs related directly to dataset that we are preparing:

- number of collected dialogues above 150
- average number of turns in dialogue around 15
- number of covered topics above 10

3.5 Usability Evaluation of ELOQUENCE Project

3.5.1 Methodology

The methodology we propose aims to integrate the metrics defined for different pilots, which were presented in the previous sections of this chapter, along with a quantitative evaluation conducted using standard tools identified through a literature review. The evaluation methodology includes two main stages to involve the entire implementation process of the pilots (see Figure 10).

- Stage 1: We plan to perform an initial evaluation of the prototype version of the Eloquence tools through the IP during the activities of T5.3.
- Stage 2: This is defined as an overtime evaluation to be conducted involving the pilot implementations during the activities of T5.5.

The results obtained will inform and improve the redesign process of the ELOQUENCE tools.

Figure 10 Usability Plan organized in two stages.

3.5.2 Evaluation Questionnaires

In the two stages described in the previous section, various measures will be evaluated to assess **user-perceived satisfaction and experience**. We selected tools based on findings from a literature search. The decision was made to use standard tools typically employed to gather user feedback in order to determine the most suitable options for KR12 and 13.

Concerning KR12 the **satisfaction feedback** is defined considering both user experience and perceived usability. The literature search has allowed us to identify in the Net Promoter Scale (NPS) (Reichheld, 2003) a concise questionnaire to assess user satisfaction, while for the usability assessment, the two tools most generically used in the literature are the UMUX (4 items) and the SUS (10 items) (Lewis, Measuring perceived usability: The CSUQ, SUS, and UMUX., 2018). Given that using both questionnaires would result in an excessive number of items, we opted for the Usability Metric for User Experience (UMUX), which is shorter and is based on the official definition and standards established by ISO 9241-11. Therefore, the choice fell on the following questionnaire

- **Net Promoter Scale (NPS):** This measures the likelihood of a user recommending a service to others. The score is collected with just one item or through a list of five questions on a Likert-type scale. This is detailed in the Appendix 6.3.
- **UMUX:** This is concise questionnaire based on the official definition and standards established by ISO 9241-11. The answers are provided on a Likert-type scale. Further details can be found in the Appendix 6.2.

In relation to KR13 and the assessment of **customer satisfaction**, several effective approaches have been identified in the literature, as for instance in (Fornell Haugeland, Følstad, Taylor, & Bjørkli, 2022) and (Feine, Morana, & Gnewuch, 2019). We consider that most appropriate for KR13:

- **Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT):** The user, after an interaction with the system, rates their satisfaction on a Likert-type scale - e.g. see Appendix 6.4. This provides immediate feedback on their experience.
- **Customer Effort Score (CES):** This assesses how easy it was for customers to resolve their issues using the chatbot, the answers are typically collected on a Likert-type scale (details are present in see Appendix 6.5).

Table 14 below summarizes the proposed tools for accessing KR12 and 13, which require answering a total of 20 questions across 4 questionnaires.

Table 14 Summarization of the questionnaire tools to evaluate user satisfaction and experience and customer satisfaction and effort.

Considered Measure	Related KR	Questionnaire	Number of items
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User Satisfaction	KR12	Net Promoter Scale (NPS)	1
Usability Experience	KR12	Usability Metric for User Experience (UMUX)	4
Customer Satisfaction	KR13	Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT)	8
Customer Effort	KR13	Customer Effort Score (CES)	7

4 Conclusions

The document outlines a comprehensive framework and methodologies for evaluating the ELOQUENCE project. It presents detailed information on the requirements, societal challenges, existing and future assets, technological needs, and pilot implementations for four distinct pilots. These pilots focus on (1) privacy-preserving language model learning, (2) social context-aware language models detecting biases, (3) retrieval-augmented LLMs as virtual agents, and (4) upgrading support call centres through AI-based supervision of multimodal dialogues.

Each pilot is discussed, including its goals, challenges, innovations, and expected outcomes. Additionally, the document provides a usability framework for assessing the ELOQUENCE tools, which incorporates both quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and metrics are defined to measure the success and effectiveness of the pilots. Finally, the usability evaluation is structured in two stages, aiming to gather user feedback and assess perceived satisfaction regarding the ELOQUENCE tools. This approach ensures continual improvement through iterative redesign processes.

Overall, the document serves as a comprehensive guide for implementing and evaluating the ELOQUENCE project. It aims to ensure that the developed technologies meet the needs of end-users and stakeholders while addressing critical societal challenges, defining baselines and metrics in relation to the KRs provided in project objectives 4 and 5. The content in this document will inform subsequent project activities, including IP implementation (T5.3), pilot integration (T5.4), and final evaluation of the pilots (T5.5), thereby contributing to the achievement of milestones in WP5 (M5.1 and M5.2).

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6 Appendix

6.1 KSVear Questionnaire

The scale KSVear (Knowledge, Skills, and Values Evaluation for Artificial Agents and Robotics), presented in Table 15, is inspired by the two established scales PSI Scale (Carpinella, Wyman, Perez, & Stroessner, 2017) and RoSAS (Barchard, Lapping-Carr, Westfall, Banisetty, & Feil-Seifer, 2018), it is developed with reference to a definition of social agent based on the theory of social practices (Reckwitz, 2002), particularly the model introduced by Frank Dignum (Dignum, 2022).

It is defined to assess the capacity of social agents to handle social practices by considering a range of items reflecting elements of the practice model, according to dimensions related to social skills, context recognition, social understanding of behaviour, and competence in managing social expectations. The items included in the scale are divided into different subscales: Social Skills, Social Understanding of the Context, Social Understanding of Behaviour, Competence in Managing Social Expectations.

Table 15 KSVear Questionnaire

KSVear Questionnaire		1 (Strongly Disagree)	2	3	4	5 (Strongly Agree)
Social Skills	<i>The agent can recognize the emotional state of the user it interacts with.</i>					
	<i>The agent can recognize the action performed by the user it interacts with.</i>					
	<i>The agent demonstrates communication skills.</i>					
	<i>The agent demonstrates expressive skills.</i>					
	<i>The agent can communicate emotions.</i>					
Social Understanding of the Context	<i>The agent has shown the ability to recognize the situation it is in.</i>					
	<i>The agent has shown awareness of its role in the situation.</i>					
	<i>The agent has been able to remember the individual it interacted with.</i>					
	<i>The agent has shown the ability to recognize the roles of others in the specific situation.</i>					
	<i>The agent has shown adequate knowledge of the situation.</i>					
Social Understanding of Behavior	<i>The agent has shown the ability to recognize others' intentions.</i>					
	<i>The agent has shown the ability to assign meaning to others' actions.</i>					

	<i>The agent has shown knowledge of the meaning of actions in the situation it is in.</i>						
	<i>The agent has shown the ability to recognize the value of actions in that situation.</i>						
	<i>The agent has shown awareness of the actions in the situation it is in.</i>						
Competence in Managing Social Expectations	<i>The agent has exhibited behaviour consistent with the specific situation.</i>						
	<i>The agent has shown competence in handling the specific situation.</i>						
	<i>The agent has adopted behavior appropriate to the ethical rules followed in society.</i>						
	<i>The agent has adopted behaviour in line with social expectations.</i>						
	<i>The agent has adopted behaviour that aligns with the social norms generally followed in the specific situation.</i>						

6.2 Usability Metric for User Experience (UMUX) Questionnaire

The items of the UMUX questionnaire are listed in Table 16. The final score is obtained with the following steps:

- odd items are scored as [user score - 1].
- even items are scored as [7 - user score].
- sum up these differences and then divide the total by 24, which is the highest possible score.
- multiplying the quotient by 100.
- averaging the results across users.

Table 16 Usability Metric for User Experience Questionnaire

UMUX	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (Strongly Agree)	NA
The system capabilities meet my requirements.								
Using the system is a frustrating experience								
The system is easy to use.								
I have to spend too much time correcting things with the system.								

6.3 Net Promoter Scale (NPS)

The item of the questionnaire is presented in Table 17. The score is calculated by subtracting the percentage of Detractors from the percentage of Promoters. The definitions are as follows:

- Promoters are respondents who scored the system a 9 or 10.
- Passives are respondents who scored it a 7 or 8.
- Detractors are respondents who gave it a score between 0 and 6.

Table 17 Net Promoter Scale

How likely are you to recommend [the ELOQUENCE platform] to a friend or colleague?"	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Example questionnaire to measure and evaluate the NPS.

1. Likelihood to Recommend:

“On a scale of 0 to 10, how likely are you to recommend our service to a friend or colleague?”

i. Scale: 0 (Not at all likely) to 10 (Extremely likely)

2. Reason for Score:

“What is the primary reason for your score?”

3. Improvement Suggestions:

“What can we do to improve your experience with our service?”

4. Specific Features:

“Which features of our service do you find most valuable?”

5. Additional Comments:

“Do you have any additional comments or feedback for us?”

6.4 Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT)

Example questionnaire to measure Customer Satisfaction Score.

Table 18 CSAT questionnaire items

Construct	Item	Scale				
Overall Satisfaction	How satisfied are you with your recent interaction with our chatbot?	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2	3	4	5 (Very Satisfied)
Ease of Use	How easy was it to use our chatbot to resolve your issue?	1 (Very Difficult)	2	3	4	5 (Very Easy)
Resolution Satisfaction	How satisfied are you with the resolution provided by our chatbot?	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2	3	4	5 (Very Satisfied)
Response Time	How satisfied are you with the response time of our chatbot?	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2	3	4	5 (Very Satisfied)
Understanding of Issue	How well did our chatbot understand your issue?	1 (Not at All)	2	3	4	5 (Completely)
Likelihood to Use Again	How likely are you to use our chatbot again for future inquiries?	1 (Very Unlikely)	2	3	4	5 (Very Likely)
Recommendation	How likely are you to recommend our chatbot service to others?	1 (Very Unlikely)	2	3	4	5 (Very Likely)
Additional Comments	Do you have any additional comments or suggestions to improve our chatbot service?"					

6.5 Customer Effort Score (CES)

Example questionnaire to measure and evaluate the Customer Effort Score.

Table 19 CES questionnaire items

Construct	Item	Scale				
		1	2	3	4	5
Ease of Resolution	How easy was it to resolve your issue using our chatbot?	1 (Very Difficult)	2	3	4	5 (Very Easy)
Effort Required	How much effort did you personally have to put forth to handle your request?	1 (A Lot of Effort)	2	3	4	5 (Very Little Effort)
Process Simplicity	How simple was the process of getting your issue resolved?	1 (Very Complicated)	2	3	4	5 (Very Simple)
Clarity of Instructions	How clear were the instructions provided by our chatbot?	1 (Very Unclear)	2	3	4	5 (Very Clear)
Time Taken	How satisfied are you with the time it took to resolve your issue?	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2	3	4	5 (Very Satisfied)
Overall Effort	Overall, how much effort did it take to get your issue resolved?	1 (A Lot of Effort)	2	3	4	5 (Very Little Effort)
Ease of Finding Information	How easy was it to find the information you needed using our chatbot?	1 (Very Difficult)	2	3	4	5 (Very Easy)
Additional Comments	Do you have any additional comments or suggestions to make our chatbot easier to use?"					